

**SOCIAL MEDIA USE AND EXPERIENCES OF URBAN YOUTH
IN MALAWI'S 2019 PRESIDENTIAL ELECTION**

**A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the
award of the degree of Master of Arts in Public Affairs and Political
Communication**

Submitted by

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Declaration

I hereby certify that this material, which I now submit for assessment on the programme of study leading to the award of master's degree (MA) in Public Affairs and Political Communication is entirely my own work and has not been submitted for assessment for any academic purpose other than in partial fulfilment for that stated above.

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Signed:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Samuel Malasa Banda', written over a faint grid pattern. The signature is enclosed within a hand-drawn circle.

Date: 01.09.2025

Abstract

Social media's influence on youth political participation has become a defining feature of contemporary elections, especially in contexts such as Malawi, where democratic engagement and electoral credibility remain contested. This thesis examines how young people in urban Malawi utilized social media during the 2019 presidential elections, focusing on the platforms they accessed, their motivations for engagement, and the meanings they attributed to their digital participation. Guided by Uses and Gratifications Theory and Digital Ethnography methods, the study conducted seventeen semi-structured interviews with urban youth, achieving thematic saturation before reaching the initial target of twenty participants. Thematic analysis showed that Facebook served as the main arena for public political discourse and information sharing, while WhatsApp offered more private and trusted spaces for discussion and mobilisation. Youth engagement was shaped by multiple motivations beyond information-seeking, including emotional support, social belonging, and reputation management. Apparent non-participation, such as silence or passive observation, often reflected strategic self-protection rather than political apathy in Malawi's low-trust political environment. Although misinformation created fatigue and scepticism, it also encouraged critical digital literacy as participants adopted verification practices and cautious sharing behaviours. Peer networks proved more influential than institutional sources in shaping credibility and mobilisation, with solidarity and emotional reassurance often taking precedence over formal political authority. Overall, youth political engagement in urban Malawi emerged as negotiated and multifaceted, combining information-seeking, identity performance, trust-building, and risk management. This challenges traditional Uses and Gratifications assumptions of rational, individualistic media consumption, showing instead that social media participation was relational, emotionally driven, and culturally situated. The study therefore provides a nuanced, context-specific understanding of how digital platforms simultaneously empowered, constrained, and transformed democratic participation for Malawian youth.

Keywords: Youth political participation; Social media engagement; Misinformation and trust; Malawi 2019 elections; Facebook; WhatsApp.

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List of abbreviations

AfCFTA – African Continental Free Trade Area
BBC – British Broadcasting Corporation
CIPESA – Collaboration on International ICT Policy for East and Southern Africa
DPP – Democratic Progressive Party
EISA – Electoral Institute for Sustainable Democracy in Africa
EEAS – European External Action Service
EU EOM – European Union Election Observation Mission
ICT – Information and Communication Technology
IDEA – International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance
IMF – International Monetary Fund
MACRA – Malawi Communications Regulatory Authority
MCP – Malawi Congress Party
MEC – Malawi Electoral Commission
MISA – Media Institute of Southern Africa
NGO – Non-Governmental Organisation
NSO – National Statistical Office
UDF – United Democratic Front
UGT – Uses and Gratifications Theory
U.S. – United States
UTM – United Transformation Movement
VOA – Voice of America
YAS – Youth and Society

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT OF RESEARCH

“Chilima has tried to capture the youth vote at these elections with an energetic social media campaign featuring hip-hop videos. That could prove to be a successful tactic as young people make up more than half of Malawi’s registered 6.8 million voters this time around.” – Reuters, 2019

1.1 Background and Context of Research

The 2019 Malawi Tripartite election was unlike any before it. A ten-month-old party without the regional or ethnic foundations that usually define Malawian politics defied expectations and captured a fifth of the national vote. How?

On 21 May 2019, Malawians went to the polls in the country's sixth democratic election since adopting multiparty democracy in 1993. Of 6.8 million registered voters, 5.1 million cast their ballots, a 74.4% turnout, slightly higher than 2014’s 70.8% (Malawi Electoral Commission, 2020, p. 37, 66). The European Union Elections Observation Mission attributed the higher turnout to several factors, including the competitiveness of thirteen candidates and the use of the national ID card as the sole registration tool, which improved the voter roll’s integrity (European Union Election Observation Mission, 2019).

Recorded as Malawi's most contested election in recent history, the Electoral Commission declared the incumbent, Professor Arthur Peter Mutharika of the Democratic Progressive Party (DPP), winner with 38.57 percent. His main challenger, Dr Lazarus Chakwera of the Malawi Congress Party (MCP), polled 35.41 percent. UTM’s Dr Saulos Klaus Chilima secured 20.24 percent of the national vote.

For many observers, this was essentially a three-horse race between Mutharika, Chilima, and Chakwera (Kainja, 2019). The United Democratic Front (UDF), once a dominant force under Bakili Muluzi, retained influence in Yao-speaking Eastern districts but managed only 4.67% under Atupele Muluzi (MEC, 2019).

The declaration of results immediately sparked contestation. Chakwera and Chilima petitioned the High Court, alleging that massive irregularities marred the election and that Mutharika was illegitimately elected (Voice of America, 2019). The petition centred on the widespread use of Tippex to alter results sheets. This raised serious concerns about electoral integrity, making verification difficult and opening the door to tampering. The opposition and civil society organisations argued that the altered results sheets undermined credibility, fuelling public distrust and ultimately contributing to the court’s decision to nullify the results (Nkhata, 2020).

On 3 February 2020, the High Court of Malawi pronounced judgment, declaring the May 2019 election null and void and ordering a fresh presidential election within 150 days (The Guardian, 2020). In the fresh election held on 23 June 2020, Chakwera and Chilima allied against Mutharika, and Chakwera won with 2,604,300 votes (59.33%), while Mutharika polled 1,752,530 votes (39.93%).

Political scientist Michael Wahman, in his paper *A Statistical Analysis of the 2019 Malawi Presidential and Parliamentary Vote: Persistence, Change, and Electoral Geography*, observes that, much like previous elections, the 2019 Tripartite election reaffirmed the dominance of regional politics. He notes: “regional politics continue to

dominate Malawian politics, and parties are tremendously effective in mobilising and consolidating their respective regional strongholds” (Wahman & Brooks, 2021, p.1).

For a clearer understanding, Kaspin (1995) offers valuable insight: “Malawian politics remain highly regionalised. Regional voting has been a constant for most of Malawi's political history, possibly except the 2009 election.” Traditionally, Malawi can be divided into four major blocs: the Southern region, the Eastern region (a sub-region of the South but distinct in voting patterns), the Central region, and the Northern region.

Building on this, Ferree and Horowitz (2010) argue that regional and ethnic dynamics have long shaped electoral outcomes in Malawi: “Malawi’s first three elections therefore resembled a ‘regional’ census: where a voter lived predicted how she voted” (p. 535). A pre-election Afrobarometer survey confirmed this, with DPP dominating the South (59%), MCP leading the Centre (55%), and the North more competitive: MCP 46%, UTM 32%, and DPP 14% (Chunga, 2020).

Given the persistence of regional voting (Wahman & Brooks, 2021), UTM’s third-place finish begs a key question: was this shift driven by digital media’s influence on youth voters?

In the run-up to the election, Reuters profiled the four leading contenders. Chilima, the UTM candidate, was highlighted as: “Chilima has tried to capture the youth vote at these elections with an energetic social media campaign featuring hip-hop videos...” (Banda & Phiri, 2019).

This question, combined with UTM’s unexpected 20.24% in 2019, forms the foundation of this research. The study seeks to explore how young people in urban Malawi experienced and engaged with social media during the elections, focusing on the meanings they attached to this engagement, the factors shaping their interactions, and how these experiences influenced political participation.

1.2 Research Objective and Question

The central research question is:

How did young people in urban Malawi experience and use social media during the 2019 elections, and what meanings did they attach to that engagement?

To address this, the study draws on two frameworks: Uses and Gratifications Theory, to explore youth motivations for social media use, and Digital Ethnography, to interpret how political meanings are constructed in digital spaces.

1.2.1 Specific objectives:

1. To explore how urban Malawian youth used social media during the 2019 election, focusing on the platforms they accessed, the content they consumed, and how they interacted.
2. To examine the motivations behind youth engagement with political content, using Uses and Gratifications Theory to understand informational, expressive, and social drivers.
3. To analyse how young people interpreted their online engagement emotionally, symbolically, and politically, using a Digital Ethnography lens to capture lived experience.

- To assess how trust, misinformation, and peer/community dynamics influenced youth political engagement online, and how these factors shaped participation.

By grounding the analysis in participants lived digital experiences, this research offers insights into how social media can simultaneously empower, mislead, connect, or isolate youth within Malawi’s democratic process.

1.3 Context of Malawi

Malawi is located in sub-Saharan Africa, with an estimated population of 20.6 million as of 2022. Like much of the region, it has a predominantly youthful population: 46% are aged 0–14, 21% aged 15–24, and only 6% aged 55 and above (World Bank, 2022).

This youthful demographic makes understanding youth political engagement, especially through social media, critical.

Figure 1: Population pyramid showing Malawi's age and gender distribution in 2022.

Often ranked among the world’s poorest countries, more than half of Malawians live below the poverty line and 25% in extreme poverty (IMF, 2022). After independence in 1964, Malawi endured decades of dictatorship that curtailed free expression. The 1993 constitution enshrined freedoms of expression, thought, and belief, but restrictive laws remain, and arrests for speech continue (Kainja, 2022). This political history frames the importance of online communication in Malawi.

1.3 Internet Access and Usage in Malawi

Economic realities shape internet access. A 2023 ICT survey found that only 3.3% of households owned a computer and just 18.4% of the population had internet access (NSO, 2024). This is due to poverty, high data costs (Kemp, 2021), limited access to devices, and low digital literacy (Kajoloweke, 2022).

Access is uneven: 44.7% of urban residents had internet access compared to 13.6% in rural areas (NSO, 2024). Connections are often intermittent (Kainja, 2019).

Yet, despite challenges, usage is rising (Kemp, 2024). Young Malawians use social media for job searches, remote work, business, entertainment, networking, activism, religion, community mobilisation, and politics (Mutsvairo & Ragnedda, 2017; Ngwira & Lipenga, 2018; Matidza, Ping & Nyasulu, 2020).

Figure 2: Social media usage in Malawi (Source: Simon Kemp).

Facebook dominates, with 63.28% of social media users, followed by Twitter (19.7%) and Pinterest (14.7%) (StatCounter, 2023).

Facebook's dominance is partly due to Free Basics, Meta's programme to expand access in the Global South (Nothias, 2020). It remains Malawi's second-most visited website after YouTube (Kemp, 2024).

Social media platforms, with Facebook as the most widely used, provide an important lens for understanding how digital political discussions unfolded among urban youth. While Facebook's dominance in Malawi is undeniable, young people also engaged with other platforms such as WhatsApp, Twitter, and Instagram, which together created a diverse digital ecosystem for political communication. Scholars have examined aspects of this ecosystem,

including the role of social media in the 2020 election, the spread of misinformation in 2019, and the influence of the diaspora in online debates (Gunde & Kainja, 2023; Kanyang'wa & Lotshwao, 2023; Nyangulu & Sharra, 2023). This study builds on that work by shifting focus from outcomes such as voter turnout to the lived experiences of young Malawians online. It asks how they used social media during the 2019 election, what motivated their engagement, and what meanings they attached to their digital participation.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction: Social Media and the Youth Vote in Malawi

Social media has profoundly reshaped Malawi's political landscape transforming citizen engagement, accelerating information flows, and altering power dynamics in the digital age. As McNair (2017, p. 11) notes, understanding political communication today requires examining how new media platforms influence the roles and responsibilities of political and public actors. In this context, social media emerges as a dynamic tool for political participation, enabling users to engage with political content in unprecedented ways (Xenos, Vromen & Loader, 2014). This shift is particularly significant in Malawi's emerging democracy, where state-controlled traditional media often fails to represent diverse voices.

Across Sub-Saharan Africa, platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter (now X), and YouTube have become essential tools for political figures, activists, and ordinary citizens (Boulianne, 2015; Farrell, 2012; Ruijgrok, 2017). WhatsApp facilitates grassroots networks that bypass top-down media structures, fostering peer-to-peer political discourse. In Malawi, traditional media outlets have increasingly integrated social media into their political coverage. During the 2020 presidential elections, major outlets livestreamed updates and used hashtags to promote real-time public conversation- "reconfiguring the dynamics of political information flow" (Gunde & Kainja, 2023, p. 147). This hybridization of communication methods, where conventional journalism blends with digital interaction has expanded both the means and rhythms of civic engagement. As Gunde and Kainja (2023, p. 148) argue, this convergence has "diversified modes of civic participation," enriching the public sphere, albeit unevenly.

Beyond Malawi, social media platforms have been used for grassroots mobilization, election monitoring, and amplifying marginalized voices (Mutsvairo & Karam, 2018; Kaufulu & Burton, 2013). These platforms offer new spaces for individual expression and political scrutiny. However, their transformative potential is constrained by the structural realities of platform capitalism. As Fuchs (2014, p. 75) cautions, "social media may stimulate public discourse, but its underlying structure is shaped by capitalist interests that serve profit rather than participatory involvement."

The 2019 Malawi presidential elections illustrated both the promise and pitfalls of social media in political communication. Facebook and WhatsApp enabled rapid dissemination of polling information, particularly among urban youth, who accessed real-time updates and engaged in unfiltered political critique (Ngwira & Brighton, 2024). Politicians increasingly used these platforms to bypass traditional media gatekeepers, engaging directly with voters through livestreams, push messaging, and digital campaign tools (Nyangulu & Sharra, 2023). This participatory communication reshaped political discourse and invited youth to construct personal and collective meanings around political events, making political talk more immediate and, in some cases, more inclusive.

A notable development during the election season was the role of diasporic influencers. These individuals used their platforms to reframe local political conversations and apply pressure on domestic actors. As Nyangulu and Sharra (2023, p. 137) observe, "diasporic influencers utilized their platforms to recontextualize political discussions and intensify political pressure on domestic stakeholders." This form of digital engagement helped dismantle

traditional barriers to participation, particularly for younger voters, by creating alternative spaces for political dialogue and challenging elite-dominated narratives (Loader et al., 2014, p. 145).

Yet, alongside these opportunities, social media also introduces significant challenges. The same platforms that foster civic engagement can become conduits for misinformation, echo chambers, and digital surveillance. Misinformation, defined as false or misleading information shared without intent to deceive (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2017)—spreads rapidly on platforms like Facebook and WhatsApp, especially in contexts of low digital literacy and high political tension. During the 2019 elections, Kanyang'wa and Letswao (2023, p. 83) documented “an unprecedented surge of misinformation,” much of it targeting electoral institutions and candidates. Even when not maliciously intended, such content can erode trust in democratic institutions and sow confusion at critical moments.

These issues are compounded by algorithmic filtering and the rise of “filter bubbles,” where users are primarily exposed to content that reinforces their existing beliefs. This limits exposure to diverse perspectives and exacerbates political polarization (Tufekci, 2015, p. 205; Ludwig et al., 2025). Moreover, digital inequalities rooted in gender, geography, and socioeconomic status shape who can participate in this evolving communicative landscape. Despite growing mobile penetration, access to digital technologies in Malawi remains uneven (Kainja, 2023, p. 5; Hivos, 2020; Freedom House, 2024). As Makoza (2023, p. 59) notes, “access to digital technologies in Malawi is unevenly distributed, shaped by socio-political contexts and infrastructural constraints.” These disparities limit the inclusivity of social media as a platform for political discourse.

Taken together, these dynamics reveal a dual role for social media in Malawi and across Sub-Saharan Africa: it serves both as a catalyst for democratisation and a source of destabilization. While it expands political participation, especially among youth, it also complicates information ecosystems and challenges institutional integrity. This research situates itself within this tension, examining how social media influenced political communication among young voters during Malawi's 2019 elections.

Specifically, this study investigates how urban youth in Malawi experienced and engaged with social media during the 2019 electoral cycle, and the meanings they attached to that engagement. It explores the platforms they accessed, the types of content they interacted with, and the motivations behind their participation whether informational, expressive, or social. It also examines how youth interpreted their digital engagement emotionally, symbolically, and politically, and how trust, misinformation, and peer dynamics shaped their participation. To guide this inquiry, the literature is anchored in two intersecting theoretical frameworks: Uses and Gratifications Theory, which helps unpack youth motivations for media use, and Digital Ethnography, which offers a reflexive lens into how political meanings are constructed and interpreted within digital spaces. Together, these frameworks enable a nuanced understanding of how social media can empower, mislead, connect, or isolate youth within Malawi's democratic process.

2.2 Digital Political Engagement: Challenges for Young Voters

Young people play a pivotal role in democratic processes, particularly in emerging democracies where they often constitute much of the population (Honwana, 2012; Sommers, 2010). In Malawi, for example, “80% of its

population [is] aged below 35” (World Bank, 2022, para. 2). Understanding young people’s political behaviour is therefore essential for analysing trends in voter participation, activism, and digital engagement. Social media has significantly reshaped how young people connect with political life, transforming their access to information, modes of self-expression, and avenues for participation. Gondwe (2010, p. 1) similarly notes that youth in Malawi have historically been a powerful political force, actively engaging in activism and challenging injustice through available communication channels.

Research consistently shows that youth are among the most active consumers and creators of digital content. Loader et al. (2014, p. 145) argue that “young citizens use social media to express opinions, mobilise peers, and challenge dominant narratives,” thereby transforming the public sphere. In Malawi, Mwambakulu and Chikumba (2022, p. 13) found that university students predominantly used Facebook and WhatsApp to engage in political discussions and access election updates. Similarly, Nyangulu and Sharra (2023, p. 139) observed that these platforms enabled youth to share political memes, join livestream debates, and respond in real time to emerging issues. These findings suggest that while the modes of engagement may vary, from memes to livestreams, the underlying function of social media as a tool for political participation remains consistent across global and local context.

Social media also provides a space for performing political identities and articulating dissent. According to Kligler-Vilenchik and Literat (2024), online platforms allow youth to express visions of change and challenge institutional silence. During the 2019 elections, Malawian youth used hashtags, reaction videos, and digital satire as tools for emotional and symbolic participation (Ngwira & Brighton, 2024). Onslow (2021, p. 15) underscores the value of these modes of engagement, noting that they “functioned as an engine of activism, mobilisation and digital leverage.” The expressive acts not only foster solidarity and visibility but also reconfigure traditional boundaries of political participation, allowing youth to assert agency in spaces often dominated by older elites.

However, access to these platforms is shaped by structural inequalities. Digital divides between urban and rural areas, men, and women, and rich and poor ultimately determines who participates and whose voices are amplified. Kainja (2023, p. 1) highlights that “achieving digital rights in the country remains a distant dream for most people due to the expensive cost of the internet, insufficient telecommunication and electricity infrastructure, restrictive legal framework, and low digital literacy.” Makoza (2023) echoes this concern, arguing that such disparities undermine equitable civic engagement. As a result, online political discourse may disproportionately reflect the perspectives of urban, male, and educated users, marginalizing broader youth voices (Gilwald, 2020).

This uneven access not only limits the democratic potential of digital platforms but also risks reproducing offline hierarchies in online spaces, raising urgent questions about equity, representation, and the future of youth political participation.

Youth engagement with digital politics is also uneven. While some young people actively participate in online advocacy and mobilisation, others adopt more passive roles, consuming content without substantive engagement. This reflects what Zohouri et al. (2020, p. 11) critique as “slacktivism,” a form of digital activism that often lacks real-world political impact. Keating and Melis (2017) reinforce this concern, noting that digital participation often

“preaches to the converted” and may fail to engage politically disengaged youth. In Malawi, youth activism is further tempered by fear of surveillance, political reprisals, and disillusionment with state institutions.

Despite these limitations, social media remains a powerful tool for political socialisation. Banda (2024, p. 26) observes that in the absence of robust civic education systems, digital platforms have filled the gap providing “a wide reach and influence that allows people to create and share their opinions on politics and other issues despite opposition virtually.” Bakker and de Vreese (2011) similarly argue that online platforms help address weak civic education by offering youth access to diverse political content and participatory opportunities.

In sum, youth political behaviour in Malawi’s digital landscape reflects both the promise and pitfalls of mediated participation. While social media empowers youth expression and networking, it also reproduces existing inequalities and carries risks of surveillance, misinformation, and disengagement. This study explores how these dynamics shaped youth engagement during the 2019 elections focusing on how urban youth used social media, what motivated their participation, and how they interpreted their digital experiences.

2.3 Filling the Gap: Youth, Social Media, and Political Participation

Social media has become a central force in electoral politics across Sub-Saharan Africa, enabling political participation, facilitating real-time public discourse, and offering new platforms for civic engagement (Mutahi & Kimari, 2017, p.14; Mutsvairo & Karam, 2016, p. 6). These platforms serve not only political leaders but also empower citizens to demand accountability, particularly in contexts of democratic transition (Chiweshe, 2017, p. 135; Mutsvairo & Karam, 2016). However, as Kainja (2023, p. 1) and others have noted, this potential is constrained by structural disparities, unequal access to digital technologies, and weak regulatory frameworks that vary across national contexts (Mutahi & Kimari, 2017; Freedom House, 2023).

In countries such as Nigeria, Kenya, Zimbabwe, and Ghana, social media functions both as a tool for mobilisation and a conduit for disinformation. Cheeseman et al. (2020, p. 149) describe platforms like WhatsApp as “closed political spaces” where false information circulates with minimal oversight, a phenomenon observed in multiple electoral cycles across the continent. This dual role of empowerment and control is particularly evident in Zimbabwe, where Chitanana (2024, p. 182) argues that social media is not a neutral space for information exchange but a contested arena for political legitimacy. Within competitive authoritarian regimes, where democratic institutions exist but are simultaneously undermined by incumbents (Levitsky & Way, 2010, p. 52), digital platforms therefore become battlegrounds for both influence and resistance.

In Ghana, Frimpong et al. (2020, p. 64) build on Berg’s (2017, p. 15) claim that social media enables more active voter engagement by transcending the limitations of traditional democratic systems. Berg (2017, p. 15) argues that “online environments provide new sites for political action which are often absent in offline spaces,” highlighting the distinction he makes between voting behaviour and broader political participation. Kenya, with one of Africa’s highest internet penetration rates at 87% (Statista, 2025), has seen digital media play a prominent role in elections since 2007. Omanga and Mainye (2023, p. 143) note, however, that while social media has significantly shaped electoral discourse, its effectiveness depends heavily on the surrounding socio-political context.

South Africa offers a compelling case study. Bosch (2017, p. 229) highlights how youth activism on X (formerly Twitter) especially through the #RhodesMustFall movement- redefined political engagement among previously disengaged youth. This shift aligns with Carpentier's (2009, p. 6) concept of sub activism: "the politics of the almost imperceptible," where every day digital actions carry political meaning. Mhlomi and Osunkunle (2017, p. 107) found that during the 2014 general election, young South Africans used social media not only to receive political information but also to engage with campaigns, express opinions, challenge mainstream narratives, and construct alternative discourses. Yet, as Fombad (2021, p. 38) warns, "the rapid spread of misinformation in digital spaces undermines the possibility of creating a deliberative political climate in Africa's fragile democracies." These examples underscore the paradox of digital media: it empowers youth while simultaneously exposing them to manipulation and democratic fragility.

Malawi's 2019 electoral process reflected many of these regional dynamics. Civil society groups, political parties, and activists actively used social media to communicate with voters and disseminate electoral information. This digital engagement mirrored broader trends in Sub-Saharan Africa, where online platforms have become vital tools for political mobilisation. However, these same spaces were exploited to spread conspiracy theories, defamatory content, and digitally manipulated imagery. Kanyang'wa and Letswao (2023, p. 84) observed that "online spaces were exploited to discredit institutions and delegitimise electoral outcomes," a concern echoed by the Malawi Electoral Commission (2020, p. 58), which documented widespread election-related misinformation. The European Union Election Observation Mission (EEAS, 2019) similarly noted that while regulatory efforts were made to ensure fair media coverage, they fell short in addressing the complex challenges posed by digital disinformation.

The 2020 Fresh Presidential Election in Malawi deepened these digital trends. As Gunde and Kainja (2023, p.150) assert, "the 2020 Fresh Presidential Election showed unprecedented level of public participation through digital media," with citizens actively engaging in debates, questioning results, and challenging official narratives in real time. Twitter appeared as a key platform for political discourse, where hashtags were used to mobilise support and shape narratives (Gunde & Kainja 2023, p.149). These developments signal a growing integration of digital media into Malawi's political culture and electoral systems.

Despite these advances, the digital divide remains a major barrier to inclusive participation. Disparities in access, digital literacy, and infrastructure determine who can contribute to online forums and whose voices are amplified. Algorithmic biases further exacerbate these inequalities. Platforms prioritise content based on engagement metrics-likes, shares, and comments—which digitally literate users are better equipped to generate. Moreover, individuals with higher social status or institutional backing often gain larger following or verified accounts, which increases their visibility. As Paul et al. (2018, p. 2) observe, "possessing a verified status symbolizes enhanced credibility in the eyes of the platform audience," thereby positioning verified users as a distinct elite network whose influence far exceeds that of ordinary users. At the same time, Gillespie (2022, p. 3) shows that platforms themselves intervene in visibility through reduction strategies such as downranking or "do not recommend," thereby skewing online discourse by privileging some voices while suppressing others.

These dynamics skew online discourse toward privileged voices, limiting the representativeness. The 2019 election in Malawi thus offers a critical lens for understanding how young people are reshaping political participation through digital platforms. It also reveals the complexities they navigate; ranging from access inequalities and algorithmic bias to institutional mistrust and misinformation. This study investigates how urban youth engaged with social media during this pivotal moment, what motivated their participation, and how they interpreted their digital experiences within the broader context of Malawi's democratic process.

2.4 Analytical Lens: Theories and Critiques

To understand how urban youth in Malawi engaged with social media during the 2019 elections, this study draws on two intersecting frameworks: Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) and Digital Ethnography. UGT explains motivations for youth engagement with political content, while Digital Ethnography provides a lens for interpreting how political meanings are constructed in digital spaces (Murthy, 2008). Together, they enable analysis of both individual agency and the socio-cultural dynamics shaping participation.

2.4.1 Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT): Understanding Youth Media Motivation

Developed by Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch, UGT posits that individuals actively select media to satisfy cognitive (information), affective (emotional), personal integrative (identity), and social integrative (connection) needs (Katz, Blumler & Gurevitch, 1973–1974, pp. 513–514). This approach positions audiences as active agents, making it highly relevant for analysing youth social media use in Malawi's 2019 elections.

Blumler and Katz (1973, p. 510) describe UGT as recognising audiences who use media “to satisfy particular needs, whether for information, entertainment, or social connection.” Whiting and Williams (2013, p. 365) similarly highlight social interaction, information-seeking, and self-expression. In Malawi, Mwambakulu and Chikumba (2022, p. 32) found that university students relied on WhatsApp for maintaining connections, receiving updates, and sharing news: “I use my smartphone to receive breaking news via WhatsApp.”

Dolan et al. (2015, p. 4) note that “engagement behaviour on social media is influenced by both intrinsic motivations and gratification expectations.” Intrinsic motivations derive from enjoyment or value, while gratifications are tied to anticipated benefits (Ryan & Deci, 2000, p. 56). This reinforces UGT's relevance in explaining youth political engagement.

However, UGT has been criticised for overstating user autonomy. Swanson (1977, p. 4) argues that it “overemphasises audience freedom and overlooks the impact of media institutions.” Tufekci (2015, p. 206) stresses that digital platforms “do not simply mirror user intent but actively structure exposure and interaction.” These critiques highlight the role of algorithms and commercial interests in shaping engagement.

In Malawi, youth with higher digital literacy and stable internet were better placed to engage, while others faced exclusion due to infrastructural and economic barriers (Kainja, 2023). These inequalities underscore the need to contextualise UGT within unequal digital environments.

2.4.2 Digital Ethnography: Meaning-Making in Networked Spaces

To complement UGT's focus on motivation, this study employs Digital Ethnography, an interpretive approach to meaning-making in digital environments (Hine, 2015; Murthy, 2008). Murthy (2008, p. 837) observes that "the rise of digital technologies has the potential to open new directions in ethnography," reshaping how researchers tell social stories. Unlike content analysis, Digital Ethnography immerses in how users interpret and assign significance to their experiences (Hine, 2015, p. 4; Pink et al., 2016, p. 20).

It extends ethnography into networked spaces, enabling study of interactions, traces, and identity performances (Murthy, 2008, p. 837; Postill & Pink, 2012, p. 123). This aligns with the study's objectives: understanding how Malawian youth used social media in 2019, and what meanings they attached. Semi-structured interviews captured narratives, emotions, and reflections, revealing motivations (information, connection, expression), affective responses (empowerment, anxiety), and meaning making (political, performative, or empowering).

Memes, hashtags, and videos, as Literat and Kligler-Vilenchik (2019, p. 1995) argue, are "shared symbolic resources ... [that] provide youth with tools to construct political meaning and connect with like-minded audiences." Such artefacts enabled youth to challenge narratives and express dissent.

The method also highlights structural inequalities. Murthy (2008, p. 838) notes that "access to the Internet continues to be stratified by race, class, and gender," mirrored in Malawi's costly, uneven connectivity. Trust and credibility were equally important: Forberg (2023, p. 4) stresses the need to negotiate self-presentation to build legitimacy, while Avram et al. (2020, p. 1) show that "exposure to social engagement metrics increases vulnerability to misinformation." Together, these perspectives position Digital Ethnography as a context-sensitive method for analysing Malawian youths' political engagement.

2.4.3 Integrating the Frameworks

By combining UGT with Digital Ethnography, this study develops a comprehensive lens for analysing youth political engagement. UGT explains why youth engaged, while Digital Ethnography shows how they made meaning from it. This dual framework captures both agency and the broader socio-technical forces shaping participation.

In Malawi's 2019 elections; where political messages were emotionally charged and strategically framed, this integrated approach is especially valuable. It illuminates how digital content influenced youth perceptions, participation, and identity in a rapidly evolving media environment.

2.5 Youth, Digital Access, and Electoral Politics in Malawi's 2019 Elections

Malawi's digital media environment, shaped by infrastructural gaps, high data costs and informal political influencers, affected how youth engaged in the 2019 elections. CIPESA (2019, p. 16) notes that "high costs of data and limited infrastructure undermine inclusive participation," while Freedom House (2020, p. 18) highlights gendered online harassment targeting women. At the same time, Kainja and Gunde (2020, p. 14) observe that social media enabled mobilisation but also exposed youth to manipulation and disinformation.

2.5.1 Structural Barriers to Youth Participation

The digital divide in Malawi shaped youth participation in the 2019 elections by determining who could access and contribute to the digital public sphere. Kainja (2023, p. 5) notes that inadequate infrastructure in peri-urban and rural areas excluded many young people from online political discourse. High data costs and unreliable connections reinforced this exclusion. A 2023 ICT survey found that only 18.4% of Malawians were online, with use concentrated in urban areas (National Statistical Office, 2024). Kajoloweka (2022, p. 6) highlights that Malawi faces some of the highest data costs in Sub-Saharan Africa, and 82.8% of non-users cited cost as the main barrier (National Statistical Office, 2024, p. 45). Market dominance by Airtel Malawi and TNM, combined with weak regulation, deepened these inequalities (Hivos, 2020; CIPESA, 2020, p. 16; Kainja, 2023, p. 15).

Even where access exists, limited digital literacy restricts meaningful engagement. The NSO (2024, p. 45) reports that 37.7% of Malawians avoid the internet due to lack of understanding, while 10.6% are unaware of its existence. Barriers are thus not only infrastructural but also cognitive and educational. Digital literacy requires more than navigation; it involves evaluating content, recognising misinformation, and understanding digital rights. Pangrazio and Sefton-Green (2021, p. 21) argue that literacy is foundational to digital citizenship; without it, individuals are unlikely to claim or defend their rights.

This challenges the view that internet access automatically produces inclusive participation. While some urban, educated youth expressed their views during the 2019 elections, many others, especially in rural areas, remained excluded due to poverty, limited education, and political disenfranchisement. Makoza (2023, p. 59) stresses that Malawi's digital divide is not only technological but rooted in policy neglect and socioeconomic inequality. These overlapping exclusions show that the digital public sphere is far from democratic.

2.5.2 Influencers and Youth Mobilisation

The 2019 elections marked a turning point in the use of social media as a political tool, with both domestic and diasporic influencers shaping the narrative. They used platforms such as Facebook Live, WhatsApp, and YouTube to mobilise support, critique government actions, and spread partisan content. Nyangulu and Sharra (2023, p. 137) argue that diasporic influencers reframed local debates with emotional urgency and oppositional energy, expanding political discourse but also intensifying polarisation.

2.5.3 The 2019 Elections: Youth as Targets and Innovators

Digital media created both opportunities and risks for youth. On one hand, youth-led initiatives promoted transparency and civic monitoring. Civil society groups and independent journalists, many youth-driven, reported irregularities, challenged official narratives, and created alternative spaces for debate. The EEAS (2019, p. 27) notes that online citizen observers played a vital role in real-time oversight.

On the other hand, youth were frequent targets of disinformation. Malanga and Boahen (2022, p. 162) documented how false content on WhatsApp and Facebook eroded trust in democratic institutions, including the judiciary and legislature. Campaigns included simulated polls and attacks on opposition candidates. Although young adults are often digitally literate, they may overestimate their ability to detect deception, especially in polarised environments

(Roozenbeek et al., 2024). In Malawi, high engagement combined with limited exposure to formal media literacy left youth particularly vulnerable (Kainja, 2023, p. 17).

Young women faced additional risks. Freedom House (2020, p. 18) and Hivos (2020, p. 11) report that politically active women and female candidates were disproportionately targeted with insults, threats, and reputation attacks. These patterns discouraged participation and reinforced offline gender exclusions. Clayton et al. (2020, p. 618) note that women candidates face “widespread verbal abuse, reputation attacks, and targeted questioning,” reflecting entrenched gender norms that cast women as outsiders. Online anonymity and virality magnified these attacks. Yeandle (2025, p. 12) observes that mobile connectivity enabled mobilisation but warns that opposition parties and civic actors raised concerns over unregulated gendered disinformation.

2.5.4 Institutional Responses and Youth Resistance

Institutional responses to digital interference were weak. The Malawi Electoral Commission lacked the mandate and capacity to monitor manipulation. The EEAS (2019, p. 21) reported a surge of unauthenticated news on WhatsApp, while MACRA acknowledged the need for regulation but had yet to act. In this gap, youth and civic actors organised independently, using hashtags, livestreams, and forums to raise awareness and challenge official narratives (Gunde & Kainja, 2023, p. 160). These efforts increased participation but, being decentralised and informal, operated without legal protection.

The 2019 elections revealed both the transformative potential and the limitations of digital media for youth engagement. Social media enabled new forms of participation, expression, and oversight, but it also reproduced structural inequalities, exposed youth to disinformation, and amplified gendered exclusions. This study examines how urban youth navigated these tensions, what motivated their engagement, and how they interpreted their digital experiences in a contested democratic landscape.

2.6 Situating Literature Within the Study

The literature reviewed has examined the influence of social media on political communication, youth engagement, and electoral processes in Sub-Saharan Africa, with particular attention to Malawi’s changing digital landscape. Grounded in Uses and Gratifications Theory (Blumler & Katz, 1973; Whiting & Williams, 2013) and Digital Ethnography (Murthy, 2008; Pink et al., 2016), this body of work highlights both the enabling and excluding dynamics of digital political participation.

Existing research emphasises social media’s role in supporting real-time dialogue, grassroots mobilisation, and alternative civic spaces among young people (Loader et al., 2014; Keating & Melis, 2017; Bosch, 2017). In contexts such as Ghana, South Africa, Nigeria, and Zimbabwe, digital platforms have become arenas for resistance and contestation (Chari, 2011; Frimpong, 2021; Onslow, 2021). In Malawi, studies by Kainja (2020), Nyangulu and Sharra (2023), and Makoza (2023) have begun to explore digital inequalities, diasporic influence, and emerging civic tech cultures.

Yet important gaps remain. The 2019 Malawian elections, among the most digitally influenced and politically contested in the country’s history, have not been fully analysed in relation to youth engagement. Little is known about how young people used social media during this period, what motivated their participation, or how they

interpreted their digital experiences. While structural barriers such as internet access and digital literacy have been noted (Freedom House, 2024; Kainja, 2023), there is limited analysis of how these intersect with youth identity, particularly for rural, female, and low-income groups.

This study addresses these gaps by investigating how urban youth in Malawi engaged with social media during the 2019 elections. Uses and Gratifications Theory is applied to explore motivations, while Digital Ethnography is used to interpret meaning-making. Together, these approaches offer a nuanced account of youth political behaviour in digital spaces. The study examines not only how young people interacted with digital content, but also why they did so and how they made sense of their engagement.

By placing youth perspectives at the centre, this research contributes to both academic debate and policy development aimed at strengthening democratic participation in emerging democracies. It sheds light on the lived digital experiences of young voters and the structural and symbolic factors shaping their political engagement.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 A Case for the Research Design

This study examines the complex role of social media in shaping youth political participation in Malawi, with reference to the 2019 presidential election. While global scholarship often presents social media as a democratising force (Fuchs, 2014; Tufekci, 2015), this research explores how digital platforms also function as contested arenas shaped by access, algorithms, and agency. It investigates the motivations, meanings, and inequalities underpinning youth political engagement online.

A qualitative approach is appropriate for understanding how young people used social media, the significance they attached to their actions, and the structures that enabled or constrained participation. Such methods allow close examination of lived experience, aligning with Mack et al.'s (2005, p. 1) view that qualitative research “seeks to understand the research issue from the point of view of the local population.” Bryman (2015) likewise argues that “qualitative research is particularly strong at uncovering meanings and the cultural practices in which they are embedded” (p. 391), making it well suited to studying political engagement in Malawi's contested electoral context.

The 2019 elections, marked by digital activity and public scepticism, provide a rich backdrop for analysing how urban youth navigated social media. As Gunde and Kainja (2023) note, “the 2019 Tripartite Elections and the subsequent 2020 Presidential Elections demonstrated that social media, especially Facebook and WhatsApp, became highly contested spaces for political expression, mobilisation, and the spread of misinformation, reflecting both hope for democratic participation and scepticism about the credibility of electoral processes” (p. 9). This study therefore treats social media not as a neutral tool but as a dynamic arena of civic expression, dissent, and identity formation.

The research draws on Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) to explain why youth engage with political content, whether for information, identity expression, or community belonging (Katz et al., 1973). These motivations are shaped by socio-technical factors, including data costs, digital literacy, and gendered online harassment. To capture these dynamics, the study integrates Digital Ethnography, which examines how meaning is constructed in online spaces (Hine, 2015; Murthy, 2008).

Following Pink et al. (2016), social media is approached as a cultural and political arena in which youth practices such as sharing memes or commenting on posts reflect broader struggles for voice and legitimacy. Highfield (2016, p. 11) similarly observes that everyday social media practices can constitute political agency, particularly when formal avenues for participation are limited or contested.

Qualitative interviews serve as the primary method, enabling engagement with participants' narratives. As Atieno (2009, p. 16) explains, such methods “can explain how people behave in ways that are hard to measure.” This is especially relevant in a digital era where a meme may carry more political resonance than a manifesto and unseen algorithms shape discourse. By focusing on urban youth, who make up more than half of Malawi's population (World Bank, 2023), the study contributes to debates on digital democracy and youth political participation in Africa.

3.2 Research Design

This study employed a qualitative design within the interpretivist tradition to examine how urban youth in Malawi experienced and used social media during the 2019 presidential election. The aim was to explore meaning: how youth engaged across platforms, their motivations, and the contexts that shaped participation.

Semi-structured interviews were chosen as the primary method because they combined structure with openness, enabling participants to reflect on their digital practices while ensuring that central themes were addressed. This was particularly appropriate given the retrospective nature of the study and the absence of digital archives, which made direct observation impracticable.

The design also recognised that young people's digital practices were shaped by wider inequalities of access and visibility. As Hine (2015, p. 16) observes, internet use is often fragmented, with different groups accessing it on different devices, doing different things with it, and expecting different outcomes.

Finally, the study treated social media as an interactive political space rather than a one-way channel. As Loader et al. (2014, p. 143) argue, social media offers young people opportunities to express political opinions, challenge dominant discourses and participate in civic debate. This emphasis on voice and meaning guided the research design and the interpretation of participants' accounts.

3.3 Research Methods

To explore how young people in urban Malawi experienced and interpreted social media during the 2019 presidential election, this study employed semi-structured interviews. This method was chosen for its capacity to capture participants' own perspectives while allowing flexibility to probe emerging themes.

3.3.1 Semi-Structured Interviews

Semi-structured interviews balanced structure with flexibility, ensuring coverage of core themes while allowing participants to shape the discussion (Rubin & Rubin, 2005; Bryman & Bell, 2015).

All interviews were conducted virtually via Microsoft Teams or Google Meet, depending on participants' preferences. Each lasted between 30 and 60 minutes, with informed consent obtained beforehand. While challenges associated with virtual methods are acknowledged in Section 3.5, the approach facilitated access to participants across multiple urban centres.

3.4 Sampling Strategy

At the outset, purposive sampling was employed to identify individuals with knowledge and experience relevant to the research topic. As Creswell and Plano Clark (2017, p. 112) note, purposive sampling enables researchers to select participants who can best illuminate the phenomenon, while Bryman (2012, p. 418) adds that this is done strategically to ensure relevance to the research questions.

Following O'Reilly's (2009, p. 193) observation that purposive sampling often attends to key social categories such as age, gender and class, the study concentrated on young people in urban centres including Lilongwe, Blantyre, Zomba and Mzuzu. These cities were selected for their higher levels of digital access and social media use, making them the sites where youth were most likely to be politically active online during the 2019 election.

3.4.1 From Purposive to Snowball Sampling

Snowball sampling was later employed to extend recruitment (Seale et al., 2006). Initial participants were accessed through youth networks, Facebook groups and WhatsApp communities, and some recommended others who met the criteria. This approach is particularly valuable when trust within social networks is essential. As Mack et al. (2005, p. 33) note, it is especially useful for hard-to-reach populations.

However, snowball sampling carries limitations. Because referrals occur within existing social circles, the sample can become skewed towards particular demographic or ideological groups (Noy, 2008), and marginalised voices may remain excluded (Biernacki & Waldorf, 1981). To address these risks, participant diversity was monitored and referrals sought across gender, educational background and political engagement. Together, purposive and snowball sampling ensured both relevance and breadth.

3.4.2 Participant Selection

Eligibility criteria required participants to have been aged 18–35 during the 2019 elections, to have lived in an urban area at that time, to have used social media during the elections, and to consent to a recorded semi-structured interview. No exclusions were made based on gender, education, employment or political orientation. The aim was to capture a range of perspectives, from highly engaged activists to more passive observers, reflecting the diversity of Malawian youth political behaviour online.

The study drew on the Malawi National Youth Policy (2023–2028) definition of youth as aged 10–35 (Ministry of Youth and Sports, 2023, p. 5) but concentrated specifically on those aged 18–35. Urban youth were prioritised because they are more likely to have consistent internet access and participate in political debate (Mutsvairo & Ragnedda, 2017, p. 7). This focus ensured that the study engaged those most positioned to shape and interpret the digital political landscape during the election.

3.4.3 Final Sample Size

Seventeen interviews were conducted. Although the target was approximately 20, data collection concluded at 17 due to thematic saturation. This number enabled in-depth engagement with each participant while still allowing comparison across experiences.

Saturation refers to the point at which no new insights emerge. Guest, Namey and Chen (2020, p. 10) suggest that for relatively homogenous populations and focused research questions, 12–15 interviews often suffice. In this study, saturation was reached when three consecutive interviews produced no new themes, when the sample reflected diversity across gender, education and political orientation, and when data included both highly engaged and more passive social media users. At that point, further recruitment was judged unnecessary.

In terms of composition, the final sample achieved variation across gender (nine male, eight female), age (19–33), and location. While Lilongwe was most represented, participants were also drawn from Blantyre, Zomba and Mzuzu, reflecting Malawi's main urban centres. Educational levels ranged from secondary school to university graduates and professionals, and political engagement varied from active campaign followers to more passive content consumers.

3.5 Limitations and Scope

This study focuses on urban youth aged 18–35 in Malawi who actively used social media during the 2019 presidential election. While it provides valuable insights into digital political engagement, several limitations shape the scope and generalisability of the findings.

3.5.1 Geographic and Demographic Focus

The research concentrates on urban centres such as Lilongwe, Blantyre, Zomba and Mzuzu, where internet access is more widespread. The 2023 NSO report shows that 40.7 per cent of urban residents had internet access compared to 13.5 per cent in rural areas, meaning the experiences of rural youth are not captured (NSO, 2023; World Bank, 2023). The sample is also skewed towards those with at least secondary education, as digital literacy and social media use strongly correlate with higher socioeconomic status. As the World Bank notes, internet use exceeds 60 per cent among tertiary-educated individuals but remains below 10 per cent among those with only primary education (2023, p. 42). Consequently, the study foregrounds the perspectives of more digitally literate youth, while those with different educational and political experiences are less visible.

3.5.2 Retrospective Data Collection

Semi-structured interviews were conducted in mid-2025, six years after the 2019 election, which may introduce recall bias. As Marshall, Rossman and Blanco note, “interview data are always partial and shaped by the passage of time, memory, and interpretation” (2020, p. 154). Participants’ reflections may have been influenced by later developments. Although this retrospective approach allowed for reflective depth, it could not capture the immediacy of lived engagement, as real-time observation was not possible (Hine, 2015, p. 56; Lundström and Lundström, 2020, p. 293).

3.5.3 Virtual Interview Constraints

Because the researcher was based in Dublin and participants were in Malawi, all interviews were conducted via Microsoft Teams or Google Meet. This offered a cost-effective way to reach dispersed urban participants but also presented challenges. Limited digital skills and unstable internet may have excluded some potential participants, and technical issues such as poor connectivity occasionally disrupted conversations. Malawi’s frequent electricity outages compounded these difficulties; at times participants were disconnected and had to re-join, while in one instance an interview continued in total darkness following a power cut, and in another, the discussion was hurried when a laptop battery began to fail. These conditions may also have constrained openness on sensitive political issues, particularly in a context of perceived online surveillance (Kanyang’wa and Letswao, 2023, p. 22). Despite these setbacks, all interviews were successfully completed, and the disruptions did not compromise the quality of the data collected.

3.5.4 Digital Ethnography Challenges

Digital ethnography was considered but proved difficult to apply due to algorithmic curation, disappearing content and the difficulty of contextualising online interactions without participant input (Tufekci, 2015; Pink et al., 2016; Masullo and Coppola, 2023, p. 6). These challenges limited its utility, so the study relied more heavily on interview narratives, which provided richer and more reliable insights into participants’ experiences.

While Digital Ethnography was considered as part of the research design (see Section 3.1), its application was limited in practice. Algorithmic curation, disappearing content, and difficulties in contextualising interactions without participant input reduced its utility for this study. As a result, interviews became the primary data source, with ethnographic elements used mainly to guide interpretation rather than to generate stand-alone findings.

3.5.5 Implications and Mitigation

These limitations do not undermine the study's value but define its interpretive scope. The findings provide a context-specific understanding of urban Malawian youths' digital media use while recognising the constraints inherent in retrospective and virtual qualitative research.

3.6 Data Analysis

In keeping with the interpretive and qualitative orientation of this study, the data were analysed using thematic analysis, a method well-suited to exploring lived experiences and meaning-making. This approach enabled the identification of key patterns across participants' narratives, moving beyond surface-level descriptions to examine how young people in urban Malawi made sense of their social media engagement during the 2019 presidential election.

Thematic analysis is particularly appropriate due to its flexibility and capacity to engage deeply with subjective experience. As Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 79) explain, it is "a method for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data."

3.6.1 Steps in the Analysis Process

Thematic analysis was conducted in an iterative manner involving transcription, coding, theme development, and interpretation, broadly following Braun and Clarke's (2006) approach. All interviews were transcribed verbatim and coded to identify recurring patterns of meaning. The initial descriptive codes are presented in Appendix 3, while the subsequent process of clustering these into sub-categories, categories, and final themes is shown in Appendix 5. This process generated key themes such as patterns of social media use, motivations for engagement, symbolic and emotional meaning-making, and the navigation of trust and misinformation, which directly addressed the central research questions. Reflexivity was integral throughout, as coding and interpretation reflected both participants' narratives and my standpoint as a researcher within Malawi's political context.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

In line with ethical research practice, all participants provided informed consent before taking part in the study. As Mack et al. (2005, p. 9) emphasise, participants must be made aware of the study's purpose, the nature of their involvement, and how the data will be used.

To protect privacy, all names and identifying details were anonymised. Pseudonyms were used in transcripts and the final write-up, unless a participant explicitly requested otherwise. While Jensen (2021) suggests that de-anonymisation may be unproblematic in non-sensitive contexts, this study involved political engagement during a contested electoral period. Anonymity was therefore strictly maintained to mitigate potential risks.

Participation was entirely voluntary. No individual was pressured to take part, and all were informed that they could withdraw at any time without consequence. During interviews, efforts were made to foster a safe and open environment in which participants could speak freely, with the option to pause or stop the interview if they experienced discomfort.

As Forbat and Henderson (2005) note, sharing transcripts or research outputs with participants can foster empowerment, though this must be approached with care. Where appropriate, a summary of the findings was offered to those who expressed interest, as a gesture of transparency and recognition of their contributions.

3.7 Researcher Positionality

I am a 32-year-old Malawian man who has participated as a voter in the 2014, 2019, and 2020 elections and actively engaged with political debates on social media during these periods. Professionally, I work with the Malawi Electoral Commission in a role that intersects with electoral processes and public engagement. These experiences shaped my interest in youth political participation but also required careful reflexivity to ensure they did not bias data collection or interpretation. As Atieno (2009, p. 15) notes, acknowledging one's position enables the researcher to critically reflect on their influence on the research process. While my perspective informed the research questions, the study remains grounded in the voices and experiences of Malawian youth.

CHAPTER 4: MAKING SENSE OF INFORMATION, IDENTITY AND TRUST ON SOCIAL MEDIA

4.1 Introduction to Finding and Analysis

This chapter draws on 17 semi-structured interviews with young Malawians aged 18–35, alongside digital ethnographic reflections, to explore how they used social media during the 2019 elections, why they engaged politically, and the meanings they attached to that engagement.

The analysis unfolds across five themes: Platform Use and Affordances, examining how youth navigated social media as political spaces; Uses and Gratifications – Information, focusing on news, updates, and decision-making cues; Identity and Symbolic Meaning, looking at how political identities were performed and negotiated; Misinformation and Trust, capturing responses to rumours and scepticism; and Peer and Community Dynamics, exploring how social networks shaped participation.

Developed inductively through thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) and interpreted using Uses and Gratifications Theory (Katz et al., 1973) and Digital Ethnography (Hine, 2020; Pink et al., 2016), the chapter uses direct quotations to foreground participants’ voices and show how emotional, symbolic, and civic meanings were woven into everyday digital practices.

Table 1 below provides an overview of the participant profile, highlighting key demographic and experiential characteristics of the sample.

Variable	Category	Total number (17), n (%)
Gender	Male	
	Female	
Age group	18 - 23 years	
	24 – 29 years	
	30– 35 years	
Education level	No education	
	Primary	
	Secondary	
	Tertiary	
	Don't know	
Region of residence	Southern	
	Central	
	Northern	

Table 1: Overview of the participant profile

4.2 Platform Use and Affordances

Young Malawians’ engagement during the 2019 elections unfolded primarily on Facebook and WhatsApp. These platforms were not simply tools but mediated environments where youth negotiated visibility, expression, and

belonging. Their use was shaped by technical affordances (Gibson, 1979, p.127), infrastructural divides, and cultural norms about what counted as safe or risky participation. In line with the first research objective, this section highlights how Facebook and WhatsApp became the core political arenas, while other platforms were strategically avoided. Taken together, the accounts show that platform use was both pragmatic and symbolic, balancing access, identity, and risk.

4.2.1 Facebook as the political front row

Participants consistently described Facebook as the main site of electoral conversation. Its attraction was partly infrastructural, given its low data use and broad accessibility, but also cultural, since it was perceived as the space where “Malawi was talking”.

“Facebook during that time? It was everything. That’s where we got results, where MEC would post things, where people would go live at rallies... you could feel the tension and excitement building right there.” (P08)

This immediacy made Facebook more than a news source. It became a participatory civic space where politics was experienced as both information and emotion. As P03 reflected:

“Instead of tuning into the TV, we can simply stream some of the programmes on their Facebook pages... I would say that, in some way, it has given a voice to the voiceless.”

Collectively, these accounts illustrate how Facebook functioned as both infrastructure and arena. This dual role echoes Bosch’s (2017, p.5) observation that African youth use social media to bypass traditional gatekeepers. Yet the benefits were uneven. Those with limited data often relied on Facebook Zero or forwarded screenshots, a reminder that what appears universally accessible often reproduces inequality (van Dijck and Poell, 2013). Thus, while Facebook anchored youth political engagement, it also highlighted the divides shaping who could participate fully.

4.2.2 WhatsApp as the quiet room

If Facebook was the public square, WhatsApp was the private room. Its encrypted, small-group format made it feel safe for trusted dialogue.

“Facebook is like a big public square... But WhatsApp is where I have more meaningful conversations with people I trust, without fear of trolls or political spies.” (P16)

This sense of privacy encouraged grassroots participation. P10 described WhatsApp groups as “critical for discussions” where people exchanged ideas, encouraged one another to vote, and even mobilised resources for campaigns. WhatsApp therefore acted as a quieter but vital civic infrastructure, aligning with Boddy’s (2014, p.56) notion of contextual privacy.

Yet trust also carried risk. As P13 explained:

“WhatsApp groups were the place where we talked seriously... But the same groups could also be stressful, like someone would forward a voice note or some conspiracy, and you do not know if it is true.”

What emerges here is WhatsApp's paradox. The intimacy that made dialogue feel safe also accelerated the spread of unchecked rumours. In Malawi's tense electoral climate, WhatsApp was both shield and sieve, a space that enabled genuine participation while exposing users to confusion and doubt.

4.2.3 Strategic avoidance of Twitter, Instagram, and TikTok

Other platforms were often bypassed. Twitter was considered "complicated", "elitist", and urban, while Facebook felt more inclusive and culturally resonant.

"Twitter may be for the urban lad, the urban person, but Facebook is for all... On Twitter, you have to type in bits. But on Facebook we have people who are like columnists... The interaction, the exchange of ideas is different."

(P03)

This contrast highlights how digital hierarchies are shaped not only by access but also by language and cultural form (Mutsvairo and Ragnedda, 2019). Facebook's mix of Chichewa, humour, and informal expression was more inviting than Twitter's English-dominated formality. Instagram and TikTok were likewise dismissed as apolitical or performative, platforms where style overshadowed substance.

Avoidance was also tactical. Participants cited data costs, fatigue, and polarisation as reasons for limiting engagement. As P06 explained:

"I had Twitter, but I did not use it much during the elections... Facebook felt closer to home."

Here we see that non-use was not simple neglect but a deliberate strategy. This selective presence illustrates what Ndlovu (2021) terms "intentional digital withdrawal", where opting out of certain platforms becomes an act of digital citizenship that reflects priorities of relevance, identity, and emotional safety.

4.2.4 Modes of interaction: visible, subtle, silent

Even within the same platform, engagement varied widely. Some participants were outspoken, posting or debating. Others signalled preference through likes, shares, or profile frames. Many engaged silently, scrolling, screenshotting, or discussing content privately.

"I followed the elections so closely, but I never commented. I would just scroll, read, click links, and sometimes screenshot posts to discuss with my sister privately. It is not that I did not have opinions, I just did not want to be out there." (P15)

This variation shows that political participation is not limited to visible expression. In Uses and Gratifications terms, even passive scrolling can satisfy needs for information, identity, and connection (Katz, Blumler and Gurevitch, 1974; Swanson, 1977). In Malawi's fragile political environment, silence itself became strategic. Choosing to observe rather than post gratified needs for safety, reputation management, and emotional control. Placed in context, these patterns challenge UGT's tendency to equate gratification with visible activity, demonstrating that non-participation can be as meaningful as overt expression in fragile democracies. This extends Uses and Gratifications Theory by demonstrating that avoidance, silence, and passive observation can themselves function as gratifications in low-trust political environments.

4.3 Uses and Gratifications – Information

4.3.1 Checking social media like the morning news

For many participants, social media functioned as the default political dashboard during the 2019 elections, a space where updates, rumours, reactions, and official statements collided in real time. In Malawi, traditional media like radio (77.3% access) and television (61.1%) retained symbolic authority but often lagged in speed and interactivity. Social media reached fewer people (28.3%) but, for politically engaged youth, offered a faster, more participatory, and immersive source of political awareness than radio, TV, or newspapers (MACRA & NSO, 2023, p. 19).

Participant 3 captured this shift in habit:

"For me, it became part of the routine, like how someone wakes up and checks WhatsApp, I would wake up and check Facebook, not for gossip, but to see what was happening in the country. Sometimes the radio was too slow. MEC would post results on Facebook before we heard them on the news. That is how I followed the elections."

This habitual checking reflects what Katz, Blumler and Gurevitch (1974, p. 20) describe as a goal-directed use of media in this case, for timely and relevant electoral information. However, in the Malawian context, it was not only about speed, but it was also about proximity. The use of the Chichewa local language, familiar idioms, and the sharing of posts by people participants knew personally created a sense of intimacy and relevance. This aligns with Straubhaar's (1991, p. 43) concept of cultural proximity, which suggests that audiences are drawn to media reflecting their own language, culture, and lived experiences.

Participant 6 reinforced this point by describing the urgency and intensity of the experience:

"During elections, things move fast. Someone might say Chilima has resigned or MEC has declared a winner. If you are offline for two hours, you come back to 50 posts. You just scroll and try to make sense. You ask, what's true? Who's saying what?"

This sense of being constantly “on call” for election updates illustrates what Pink et al. (2016, p. 43) conceptualise in Digital Ethnography, not the passive consumption of information, but the active navigation of a dense social field where news is entangled with relationships, loyalties, and political identities. In this context, the “scroll and make sense” behaviour was as much about situating oneself within the political conversation as it was about acquiring facts.

Patterns like these were not isolated. Across the interviews, overreliance on social media was intensified by the uncertainties of the 2019 elections and, ultimately, the court-sanctioned rerun in 2020. For young people in urban areas with access to social media, peer commentary and viral content made the online space both indispensable and chaotic. Nevertheless, it remained a central channel for staying politically informed illustrating what Bradshaw and Howard (2019, p. 5) call the double-edged nature of social media, which simultaneously enables civic awareness while fostering disinformation and polarisation. From a Uses and Gratifications perspective, this reflected an information-seeking motive that persisted despite the platform’s chaotic environment, as participants were willing to tolerate uncertainty and misinformation to remain embedded in the political conversation.

4.3.2 Learning politics through the feed

For many participants, the 2019 presidential election was the first-time politics felt immediate, personal, and unavoidable. This shift did not result from formal civic education but from the constant scroll of the social media news feed.

Participant 14 reflected on how her understanding of Malawi's electoral process changed during this period:

"Before 2019, I honestly did not know what MEC did. I just thought they count votes. However, then I saw posts explaining how the commission works, what people were protesting about, and even the court case after the election. I learnt more from Facebook than from any teacher."

Participant 1 echoed this sense of political discovery:

"Some people were even interpreting some of the issues happening in court, maybe the witnesses. When they were giving their testimony in court, some people would even start analysing what was happening in court. So, it gives me curiosity to continue being on social media and seeing and talking about what is happening and also understanding what is happening and how it will shape our future."

These were not isolated experiences. Across interviews, young people described stumbling into civic education through memes, infographics, live-streamed press conferences, and lengthy comment threads where strangers debated constitutional provisions. In a country where, as Chibambo and Divala (2023, p. 2) note, "civic education in Malawi has largely been sporadic, often externally funded, and implemented around election cycles, with little sustained integration into the formal education system," the 2019 elections transformed social media into an informal yet powerful civic classroom.

However, unlike a structured curriculum, this "syllabus" was unpredictable. One day the feed might be filled with detailed legal analyses of a court ruling; the next, with satirical skits mocking political leaders. The result was a form of learning-by-osmosis, where political knowledge was pieced together from multiple voices, often with clashing perspectives.

From a Uses and Gratifications perspective, this behaviour partially aligns with the notion of cognitive gratification: the active pursuit of knowledge to satisfy curiosity or to make sense of political events (Kaye & Johnson, 2002; Whiting & Williams, 2013). Yet the Malawian case complicates this picture. Rather than seeking information in a structured, goal-oriented manner, participants navigated a fragmented and emotionally charged environment shaped by memes, rumours, and personal commentary.

This echoes Windahl's (1981) critique that UGT risks portraying audiences as overly rational and instrumental, overlooking the emotional, habitual, and socially embedded dimensions of media use. Similarly, Ruggiero (2000) notes that UGT often underestimates the relational contexts in which information is consumed and interpreted. The experiences of Malawian youth suggest that information seeking during the elections was not simply about acquiring facts but about navigating uncertainty, emotion, and social meaning. Learning politics on social media was therefore active but rarely linear, rational, or predictable.

4.4 Identity and Symbolic Meaning

On social media, the 2019 presidential election in Malawi was more than a contest over policies, votes, and court verdicts; it was also a moment of symbolic meaning-making. For many young Malawians, platforms became both a mirror and a stage where political identity was performed, concealed, or subtly coded. These performances drew on conviction, culture, religion, and risk management. As Gunde (2020, p. 44) observes, online political expression in Malawi often weaves together religious and cultural identities with political narratives, making digital engagement inseparable from broader identity work. This highlights that youth participation must be understood not only in terms of content but also through the symbolic repertoires by which identity was negotiated.

4.4.1 Performing and Protecting Identity

Social media offered visibility, but in Malawi's charged climate visibility carried risk. Posts were rarely directed at a single audience; colleagues, relatives, church elders, and political rivals all occupied the same digital "room." This is a form of context collapse (Marwick and boyd, 2011), where messages reach unintended audiences, heightening the stakes of political speech by tying it to reputation, career, and even safety.

Participant 13, a banker in Blantyre, described this clearly:

"I wanted to say things sometimes, like when people were attacking Chilima or talking nonsense about rigging. But then I'd remember: my manager is on Facebook. Some clients follow me. And even church friends. So, I just never commented. I'd read and move on."

Her silence was not apathy but identity protection. Bosch (2017, p. 223) similarly notes that African digital publics are rarely free spaces but demand reputational safeguarding. Participant 10 described how organisational rules reinforced this caution, while Participant 14 highlighted how audience reactions and shifting political moods shaped self-presentation.

Across these accounts, clear patterns emerge. All three participants recognised the risks of being "too visible" politically, yet each managed those risks differently: through anticipatory silence (P13), formal compliance (P10), or adaptive filtering (P14). What unites them is the recognition that not posting was itself a political act. Silence, deletion, and selective visibility became tools for shaping how political identity was perceived and by whom.

Theories of context collapse typically emphasise its silencing effect, yet these Malawian accounts show that young people also exploited collapse creatively. Through ambiguity, symbolism, and coded language, they remained politically visible without full exposure. Rather than simply constraining expression, context collapse here generated inventive repertoires of subtle participation, an extension often overlooked in the literature. By highlighting coded symbolism, ambiguity, and faith-based restraint as political strategies, this study extends theories of context collapse, showing how young people actively managed identity within overlapping audiences.

4.4.2 Symbolic Politics and Subtle Signals

Alongside restraint, many participants expressed political preference through subtle, symbolic cues: a profile picture change, a proverb in a status, or a meme carrying cultural meaning. These low-risk signals were easily legible to insiders yet ambiguous to outsiders.

Participant 16 explained:

“People fight too much in the comments. It drains you. But changing my profile picture to the party colours, that’s enough. Those who know, they know.”

Here, symbolism became a double-coded act: personal style to outsiders, political allegiance to insiders. Mangeya (2022) describes these as “markers of belonging.” Similarly, Participant 9 noted that even a proverb could communicate alignment without naming names. Such practices reflect folkloric traditions where proverbs and metaphors serve as subtle forms of resistance (Mpofu, 2021; Filani, 2023).

These findings suggest that symbolic participation was not secondary to explicit debate but a central mode of political engagement. By posting a proverb or changing a profile picture, youth adapted to context collapse, signalling identity in ways that were safer and more sustainable in politically sensitive environments. In doing so, they demonstrate that context collapse did not simply narrow participation but also encouraged inventive forms of coded visibility. This extends theories of digital publics (Mpofu, 2021; Filani, 2023) by showing how folkloric and cultural repertoires were re-purposed as tactical resources for online political identity.

4.4.4 Aesthetic and Cultural Resonance

Social media feeds during the campaign were saturated with performances of identity as much as with arguments. Style, humour, and cultural references often carried more persuasive power than manifestos.

Participant 8 described UTM’s Saulos Chilima as relatable:

“He felt like us... joking, using proverbs, going live. I didn’t even know the full manifesto, but I liked how he represented youth, confident, modern, not boring.”

Similarly, Participant 1 recalled:

“As a youthful leader he related much to us... doing push-ups on the podium or using words relatable to the youth, like *musamangoshala anyamata* [don’t just be idle young people].”

Chilima’s persona exemplified cultural proximity (Straubhaar, 1991), blending English and Chichewa with humour and performance. On Facebook and WhatsApp, these traits were amplified through memes and livestreams, producing intimacy and immediacy that traditional rallies could not match. Female politicians also resonated when they grounded messages in everyday struggles such as school fees or safety, consistent with Onuch et al.’s (2021) observation that personalised communication heightens perceived relevance.

The implication is clear: youth engagement was driven as much by affective and cultural resonance as by policy substance. Digital politics in Malawi cannot be reduced to rational information exchange; it was sustained through humour, style, and cultural familiarity that made leaders feel accessible and credible. This supports arguments about cultural proximity (Straubhaar, 1991) and personalised politics (Onuch et al., 2021), but it also extends them by showing how aesthetic performance became a form of political legitimacy in its own right. Malawian youth were not persuaded only by manifestos but by leaders’ ability to inhabit cultural idioms and styles that resonated with everyday life.

4.4.5 Faith, Morality, and Digital Restraint

For some participants, engagement was defined less by expression than by restraint. In Malawi, where over three-quarters of the population identifies as Christian and faith is deeply woven into public life (U.S. Department of State, 2019), political discourse was often shaped by moral frameworks. As Chanvised (2021, p. 88) observes, online political participation is not merely an exchange of opinions but also a performance of values, where individuals consciously align contributions with moral expectations.

Participant 15 illustrated this:

“Even when I agreed with some posts, I wouldn’t share them because of the way they were written, full of insults. As a Christian, I believe you should speak the truth with love. So, I just stayed quiet. But I prayed for the country.”

Participant 5 offered a similar analogy:

“If I want to criticise, I will do it in a way that my pastor can read and not feel embarrassed. Facebook is public, like standing in the market with a loudspeaker.”

Such accounts show that restraint was not withdrawal but moral self-presentation. Bosch (2017, p. 226) argues that African digital publics are shaped by normative boundaries, and in Malawi these boundaries were infused with Christian values. Gunde (2015) similarly highlights how expressions of political identity are layered performances, blending religion, morality, and coded political signals.

The broader insight here is that faith-based moderation worked as a political strategy. Silence and restraint aligned visibility with moral expectations while avoiding reputational damage. Far from apolitical, these practices demonstrate how morality and faith shaped participation in Malawi’s value-laden digital public sphere. This confirms Bosch’s (2017) claim that African digital publics are shaped by normative boundaries but also refines it by showing how Christian morality in Malawi functioned as both a filter and a mode of participation. In this sense, restraint was not absence but a moralised form of digital citizenship.

4.5 Misinformation and Trust

Beyond the management of identity, participants’ accounts revealed how misinformation directly shaped their everyday digital routines. In the 2019 elections, it was not peripheral but constant, woven into WhatsApp audios, Facebook posts, and partisan commentary that blurred the line between fact and rumour. What unsettled participants was not only the difficulty of sorting truth from falsehood but also the emotional and social effort this sorting required.

This section addresses the fourth research objective by examining how misinformation and trust shaped youth political engagement online. Uses and Gratifications Theory (Katz et al., 1973; Ruggiero, 2000) highlights how the search for reliable information collided with digital noise, weak institutional trust, and peer influence, while Digital Ethnography (Pink et al., 2016) reveals misinformation as a lived experience demanding constant interpretation and judgement.

Three dynamics dominated youth narratives: the emotional costs of information overload, the turn towards social trust and informal verification, and the learning, caution, and agency developed through misinformation exposure.

4.5.1. Information Overload and Emotional Fatigue

For many participants, the 2019 elections unfolded not only as a political event but as a daily flood of competing claims, rumours, and reactions across Facebook and WhatsApp. What was striking in their accounts was the sense of intensity of being constantly connected yet rarely certain. One participant explained,

“It is a good space, especially when you are learning from people who are knowledgeable or even experts in the field. But at the same time, it is also a space where people can spread lies, even about very important matters. When there is too much information on your plate, and too many voices speaking on the same topic, it becomes hard to know what really matters. It is difficult to figure out which voice to trust.” (P7)

This feeling of saturation reflects what Tufekci (2015) calls algorithmic gatekeeping, where the design of platforms amplifies some voices while hiding others, producing visibility without clarity. In the Malawian case, as Kanyang’wa and Letswao (2023, p. 83) note, the absence of rapid, credible communication from official institutions left rumours to “fill the vacuum of official silence.” For young voters, the result was a digital space buzzing with urgency but short on certainty.

Emotionally, this was exhausting. Several participants described the fatigue of logging in each day only to be met by conspiracy theories, fake resignations, and angry comment threads. One recalled,

“There were days I would open Facebook and just sigh. Rigging stories, court battles, fake resignations. And the comments were worse, people insulting each other. You want to know the truth, but the more you read, the more confused you get.” (P13)

Their reflections suggest that the problem was not simply *false* information, but the *relentless volume* of competing claims and emotional reactions. As Jiang (2022, p. 6) observes, information overload often leads to “fatigue, exhaustion, and eventual withdrawal,” a pattern visible here as participants spoke of unfollowing accounts, muting contacts, or avoiding comment sections altogether.

Some turned to selective participation as a coping strategy. One explained,

“Sometimes when I see this is too much, I just unfollow the person. Or even block them if they are posting lies. I have done that several times when I see they are posting things that are not true or that I do not like.” (P14)

Others became more cautious rather than withdrawing completely:

“I do not fully trust social media. What I do is start verifying. If I know someone with better access to information, I will call them. If I do not, I will go to more reliable sources, maybe official pages or credible media houses like Times.” (P6)

This suggests not apathy but adaptation. Young people negotiated between wanting to stay informed and protecting themselves from emotional and cognitive overload. As Qin et al. (2024, p. 3) argue, this is a common response when users face “excessive and ambiguous information” that threatens to overwhelm rather than enlighten. In Malawi, it

meant political engagement became more cautious, private, and filtered through personal networks, shaping not only *what* young people knew but *how* they participated in the electoral conversation.

4.5.2 Social Trust and Informal Verification

Amid the flood of political content, young Malawians rarely abandoned social media altogether. Instead, they developed what several participants called a habit of scepticism, a set of practices for verifying, cross-checking, or delaying judgement before sharing, commenting on, or even believing political updates.

“I do not fully trust social media. What I do is start verifying. If I know someone with better access to information, I call them. If I do not, I go to official pages or credible media houses like *Times 360*.” (P6)

This behaviour reflects what Koivunen and Vuorelma (2022, p. 395) call strategic trust, where credibility depends on personal networks, reputation, and lived experience rather than institutional authority. Participants rarely relied solely on official accounts or platform tools. Instead, as Eveleth et al. (2024, p. 3) note, experiences of both benefit and risk shape users’ trust decisions, pushing them toward selective trust and controlled sharing in uncertain digital spaces.

The absence of institutional trust was striking. Several participants doubted MEC’s impartiality, especially during post-election disputes. Cheeseman et al. (2018, pp. 5–7) note that when electoral bodies fail to deliver timely and transparent information, official channels risk losing authority, creating conditions for confusion, distrust, and competing claims. Over time, this erosion of confidence in state actors can push citizens to seek information elsewhere. In weaker democracies, informational legitimacy often shifts toward informal networks, a pattern clearly visible in Malawi.

As Kanyang’wa and Letswao (2023, p. 87) observe, MEC’s slow digital response during the 2019 elections created a vacuum in which rumour thrived, leaving peers and personal contacts to fill the gap. Faced with this uncertainty, Malawian youth increasingly relied on trusted social networks rather than official sources.

One participant explained this shift clearly:

“I have learned not to trust the first post I see. I wait three or four hours to see if it will be confirmed. Sometimes it ends up being true, sometimes false. My trust in these pages is maybe 70%, because some of what they post is right, but there is always exaggeration.” (P13)

Verification, therefore, was not simply about factual accuracy. It was also a social and political act. Whether one commented on a post, defended a candidate, or joined a WhatsApp debate often depended on whether the information came through trusted networks rather than unknown pages.

This reliance on peers for verification aligns with Kanyang’wa and Letswao’s (2023, p. 87) finding that political information in Malawi frequently travels through relational gatekeeping, where peers negotiate trust before information reaches wider audiences.

Understood ethnographically, these were not abstract behaviours but everyday practices: calling a cousin who “follows politics closely,” cross-checking party pages, or waiting for contradictions before taking a stand.

Considered alongside Uses and Gratifications Theory, they reveal how informational motives overlapped with social and emotional needs.

Therefore, while young Malawians actively sought political knowledge, they were equally concerned with protecting their reputations, avoiding embarrassment, and maintaining credibility among peers. Seen in this light, these experiences show that in a chaotic digital environment, filtering the noise becomes an act of self-preservation before the noise overwhelms you.

4.5.3 Learning, Adaptation, and Digital Literacy

Encounters with misinformation during the 2019 elections did not simply frustrate young Malawians; they reshaped how many approached political information online. Rather than abandoning social media, participants described how repeated exposure to false content encouraged habits of scepticism, delayed judgement, and verification. This reflects what Tandoc et al. (2019, p. 9) term misinformation regret, where the embarrassment or frustration of sharing false content leads users to adopt more cautious information practices in the future.

For some participants, misinformation prompted greater caution before reacting or sharing. As one explained:

“It changed my perspective because sometimes, especially when people are putting out posts for breaking news... most of the times some information that is misleading it’s because some people want to be the first ones to break the news... So that had to give me a bit of time first of all not to trust every information that is posted... I have to gather the information from different sources so that I should find the right information that I am seeking.” (P1)

This shift towards caution reflects Nielsen and Graves’ (2017, p. 4) observation that when misinformation proliferates, audiences increasingly rely on trusted sources, both institutional and interpersonal, to authenticate information. In the Malawian context, this often-meant consulting friends who “follow politics closely,” cross-checking familiar media pages, or waiting to see whether a story was contradicted before engaging further.

Several participants described how these experiences developed into lasting habits of verification. One explained:

“It really changed my perspective... it taught me not to trust everything I see, no matter how good it looks, or how many people are praising it, unless I verify it first. I usually cross-check with other sources, especially reputable media houses here in Malawi or official pages. I do not just accept something and say, ‘That is it.’ I acknowledge it, but then I say, ‘OK, now let us verify.’” (P7)

Such accounts support Kanyang’wa and Letswao’s (2023, p. 87) argument that the 2019 elections inadvertently strengthened digital literacy in Malawi as young people learned to anticipate bias, question motives, and triangulate sources before making political judgements.

Some participants even viewed misinformation as a reluctant teacher rather than simply a negative force. As one put it:

“For me, I take fake news as a blessing in disguise... it keeps us on our toes... making us think, making us look for pointers that this is genuine... you do not need to lose trust in social media, all you need to do is make sure you verify.” (P17)

This perspective complicates dominant misinformation research, which often frames false content as purely corrosive to democracy. de Ridder (2021, pp. 2971–2973) argues that misinformation also provokes epistemic vigilance, forcing individuals to evaluate sources, weigh credibility, and adapt information practices. In the Malawian case, young people interpreted misinformation as sharpening their scepticism and encouraging verification, challenging Global North assumptions that exposure to falsehoods inevitably undermines civic trust.

Here, misinformation addressed what Uses and Gratifications Theory calls *cognitive needs*, the search for knowledge, understanding, and self-protection (Katz et al., 1973, p. 514; Dolan et al., 2015, p. 262). Rather than consuming information passively, young Malawians became active interpreters, weighing risks before engaging publicly.

Overall, misinformation was not only a content problem but also a learning environment, compelling youth to adapt and develop habits of critical thinking, emotional regulation, and informal verification (de Ridder, 2021, pp. 2971–2973). Truth was not simply discovered; it was actively constructed through relationships, technological constraints, and evolving digital literacy.

4.6 Peer and Community Dynamics

Engagement on social media during the 2019 elections was rarely individual. Across interviews, participants described how peers, relatives, and online groups shaped what they saw, believed, and shared. This echoes BBC News' (2018) research across several African countries, showing that trust on online platforms often fosters misinformation because people tend to believe information shared by someone they know or respect rather than scrutinising it critically.

Political conversations often began in private rather than public spaces. One participant explained:

“My interaction on social media is not about commenting or writing or sharing, but rather just reading... then I will take a screenshot of what has been posted or maybe get a link to that post and send it to them. Then we discuss it privately... with my close friends whom we share a lot in common.” (P1)

Here, social media posts became starting points for offline or private dialogue, where meaning was negotiated before any public engagement. This reflects Larsson et al.'s (2024, p. 57) observation that meaning making online and offline involves “interactive processes through which shared meanings are established.” In the Malawian case, these processes positioned political engagement as collective rather than individual.

Peer networks also enabled mobilisation and collective monitoring. Several participants described how online groups coordinated voting and even vote protection:

“People were discussing, sharing, encouraging one another to vote... even some groups were being formed just to discuss how they would guard the votes... to be involved in strategies to control rigging.” (P11)

Such practices align with Katz et al.'s (1974, p. 513) concept of integrative needs, where mass communication fosters solidarity and shared purpose within communities.

At times, these networks outpaced formal institutions in spreading information. One participant recalled:

“Before the official results were announced, party monitors had already taken photos of result sheets from polling stations. These were shared widely on social media... people did not need to wait for MEC to declare a winner as they had already formed a conclusion from what was circulating online.” (P8)

Yet the same networks also imposed subtle pressures. Another participant admitted:

“These people silently operate as gatekeepers... every time I think about posting something controversial, I have to consider how it will impact others, starting with my political party.” (P13)

Peers thus acted both as enablers and as constraints, encouraging participation while policing its boundaries.

Finally, peer alerts often determined when participants engaged with political content:

“There are moments when someone might alert me to something I have missed... like, ‘Hey, did you see what is happening on Facebook?’ That might prompt me to check it out.” (P9)

Information flow therefore relied on overlapping social ties, with friends and relatives acting as both filters and amplifiers, shaping exposure, interpretation, and response.

In line with research objective 4, these findings show that trust and participation were negotiated collectively, as informal gatekeeping within peer networks shaped both access to information and confidence in acting on it. Yet existing trust research often assumes verification seeks factual accuracy. Studies reveal that high trust in peers or institutions can actually reduce people’s motivation to authenticate information, as they rely on credibility cues or solidarity rather than critical evaluation (Pennycook & Rand, 2021; Talwar et al., 2019; van Zoonen et al., 2024).

In Malawi, youth often valued reassurance and belonging over objective accuracy. This suggests that gratifications in collective settings extend beyond cognitive needs for knowledge to include emotional validation and social anchoring (Katz, Blumler & Gurevitch, 1974; Dolan et al., 2016). By highlighting this, the study refines Uses and Gratifications Theory, showing that in fragile information environments, peer interactions fulfil both informational and affective needs.

Across all five themes, the analysis reveals that young Malawians used social media during the 2019 elections not only to gather information but also to navigate identity, trust, and community in highly charged digital spaces. Facebook and WhatsApp emerged as key arenas for news, debate, humour, and civic learning, yet they were equally shaped by misinformation, caution, and peer influence. Engagement ranged from public posting to silent observation, with even small acts such as profile picture changes or private discussions carrying symbolic weight. Political participation online was therefore both expressive and restrained, personal and collective, as youth made sense of democracy within the rhythms of everyday digital life.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION

This thesis set out to explore how young people in urban Malawi experienced and used social media during the 2019 presidential elections, and the meanings they attached to that engagement. Social media was not treated as a neutral democratic tool but as a contested space shaped by power, identity, community, and inequality. While studies from the Global North often emphasise the democratising potential of digital platforms (Fuchs, 2014; Tufekci, 2015), this research located Malawian youth within their own socio-technical realities, characterised by high data costs, state surveillance, misinformation, and peer scrutiny (Kanyang'wa & Letswao, 2023; Kainja & Gunde, 2023; Nyangulu & Sharra, 2023).

The study originally aimed to conduct twenty semi-structured interviews, but data collection concluded at seventeen when thematic saturation was reached, as further interviews produced no new insights (Guest et al., 2020; Hennink & Kaiser, 2022). These interviews were analysed thematically using Uses and Gratifications Theory (Katz et al., 1973; Ruggiero, 2000) and Digital Ethnography (Pink et al., 2016). Together, these frameworks revealed how Malawian youth used social media, primarily Facebook and WhatsApp, with occasional use of Twitter/X or Instagram to access political information, express themselves, and negotiate identity and trust. The analysis addressed four objectives, each offering a lens into the layered nature of digital media use.

The first objective examined how young people used social media during the elections, focusing on the platforms they frequented. Findings showed Facebook dominating because of its accessibility, cultural centrality, and public reach, while WhatsApp offered private, trusted spaces for dialogue. Other platforms such as Twitter/X and Instagram appeared occasionally but played a much smaller role. Participants navigated primarily between Facebook and WhatsApp to balance visibility with caution, using them not only for information but also for validation and connection. These patterns echo broader African findings, where Facebook often functions as the central public arena and WhatsApp as a more intimate site of mobilisation and debate (Omotayo & Folorunso, 2020; Adegbola & Gearhart, 2019). In Malawi, Nyangulu and Sharra (2023) similarly highlight how Facebook was leveraged by diasporic influencers and local youth to mobilise support, shape narratives, and negotiate political credibility.

The second objective explored the motivations behind youth engagement. While information-seeking was central, participants also described emotional, social, and reputational considerations shaping their behaviour. Silence, lurking, or avoiding debate frequently emerged as strategies of self-protection rather than apathy, reflecting the risks of visibility in a low-trust political environment. Uses and Gratifications Theory accounts for this, recognising that media use addresses not only cognitive but also social integrative and affective needs (Katz, Blumler & Gurevitch, 1974). Bosch (2017) likewise observes that African youth navigate political expression through a tension between participation and caution. In Malawi, Kainja and Gunde (2023) show that political expression online is often filtered through cultural and social considerations, making non-participation or silence itself a meaningful act of engagement.

The third objective considered how young people made sense of their engagement. Social media was not merely a channel for consuming political news; it was also a stage for identity performance. Memes, profile picture changes, and coded posts carried symbolic significance as participants managed how their digital selves were interpreted by peers, employers, and wider communities. This reflects Marwick and boyd's (2011) notion of context collapse, where multiple audiences converge online, requiring careful self-presentation. Bosch (2017) similarly shows that African youth balance expression with restraint, while Ngwira and Brighton (2024) highlight how Malawian memes and proverbs carried insider political meanings, allowing subtle and ambiguous participation. These findings suggest that identity-making on social media was both expressive and strategic, rooted in cultural forms that allowed young people to engage without overexposing themselves.

The final objective examined trust, misinformation, and peer dynamics. Participants relied less on institutional sources or platform tools than on personal networks to verify information, reflecting what Koivunen and Vuorelma (2022, p. 395) call strategic trust, where credibility depends on relationships and lived experience. Encounters with misinformation produced fatigue and scepticism, consistent with Jiang's (2022) argument that information overload often leads to withdrawal or cautious engagement. In Malawi, Kanyang'wa and Letswao (2023, p. 87) note that slow institutional responses left space for peer networks to dominate verification and meaning making. These networks both empowered and constrained: they offered solidarity and reassurance but also enforced silence through peer pressure or fear of judgement. BBC News (2018) likewise found across African contexts that trust in relatives or peers often substitutes for critical evaluation, amplifying both accurate and misleading information.

Seen across the four objectives, this thesis shows that young people in urban Malawi experienced the 2019 elections through digital spaces that were at once informative, social, and emotionally charged. Social media use was shaped by platform affordances, motivations that blended curiosity with caution, identity performances balancing visibility and risk, and peer networks that enabled both solidarity and constraint. Misinformation complicated these dynamics, at times eroding certainty yet also fostering scepticism and digital literacy.

By combining Uses and Gratifications Theory with Digital Ethnography, the study demonstrates that youth political engagement online cannot be reduced to access or activity alone. It was a negotiated process in which information seeking, emotional self-protection, identity-making, and collective trust-building unfolded simultaneously. Social media during Malawi's 2019 elections was therefore not only a tool for political participation but also a site where democracy itself was experienced, interpreted, and contested in real time.

5.1 Critical Reflection

While this thesis demonstrates how Malawian youth stretched existing theories of media use and digital participation, its own scope was also bounded by limitations. My focus on urban youth, for instance, left the experiences of rural young people unexplored, even though they navigate different infrastructural and political realities that might challenge the findings further. Another limitation lies in the retrospective nature of the interviews, since I asked participants in 2025 to recall their engagement in the 2019 elections. Their accounts may have been shaped by hindsight and later political developments.

Although themes of gender, class, and religion surfaced in the data, I did not examine these systematically. Future research could take a more intersectional approach to show how overlapping identities shape digital political life. Studies might also compare rural and urban youth, track participants across an electoral cycle, or investigate the growing role of digital influencers on Facebook Live, TikTok, and Twitter Spaces. Comparative work across African democracies would further illuminate shared and divergent trajectories in youth, technology, and political participation.

Even with these limits, I believe the thesis contributes to knowledge by centring Malawian youth in debates on digital politics, a group often overlooked in the literature. The findings show that engagement during the 2019 elections was about more than information seeking; it also involved negotiating identity, trust, and community within unequal digital environments. By combining Uses and Gratifications Theory with Digital Ethnography, I have provided a context-specific account of youth political meaning-making online, adding depth to wider discussions of technology and democracy in Africa.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Interview Guide

INTRODUCTION

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this interview, which will take about an hour. I'm conducting this research as part of my master's in public Affairs and Political Communications studies at Technological University Dublin, and I'm interested in understanding how young people in Malawi used social media around the 2019 presidential election, what kinds of content you engaged with, how it made you feel, and what it meant to you. There's no pressure to give perfect answers, this is really about your story and experience. Everything you share will be confidential and used only for academic purposes. You can skip any question or stop at any point if you wish.

SECTION A: Background and Digital Habits

1. Can you tell me a bit about yourself? (Education, urban vs rural, etc.)
2. How did you get started using social media?
 - What motivated you to begin, and what platforms did you start with?
3. Tell me how you use social media?
4. Has your social media usage changed over time?
 - If so, what caused those changes?
5. Do you tend to use one platform more than others, like social media instead of radio or newspapers, for political content?

SECTION B: Motivations and Meaning-Making (UGT Lens)

6. What kind of stuff do you usually look at on social media?
7. Can you tell me about powerful or memorable experiences that you have had through social media?
8. Do you think your social media presence reflects who you are offline?

SECTION C: Influence, Identity, and Interaction

10. How do people around you, i.e., friends, family, classmates or workmates, influence how you use social media?
11. Have you ever held back from saying or sharing something online because of how others might respond?
12. What accounts/pages/ individuals do you find most important or influential in your social media circle?
13. Have you ever come across posts that turned out to be false or misleading?
 - How did that affect your trust or use of social media?

SECTION D: Elections and Political Experience

15. Thinking back to the 2019 elections, what do you remember about how people, including yourself, were using social media?
16. What kinds of political or election-related content stood out to you during that time?
17. Do you think social media has changed how people were involved or informed during that election?
18. How were people your age engaging with politics online during that time?
19. Do you feel that being online during the 2019 elections had any impact on how people think about politics or their role as a citizen?

Wrap-Up

20. Is there anything else you'd like to share? Is there anything we haven't talked about?

Participant Consent Form: Social Media Use and Experience Among Urban Youth During Malawi's 2019 Elections

This form is part of a research project conducted by Samuel Malasa Banda of Technological University Dublin, which explores how young people in Malawi used social media during the 2019 presidential election.

You are invited to take part in a research interview exploring how young people in Malawi used social media around the 2019 presidential election, the kinds of content they engaged with, how it made them feel, and what it meant to them. The research is part of a postgraduate study in Public Affairs and Political Communication at Technological University Dublin.

Please read the following information carefully before you agree to participate.

You will be asked questions about your experience using social media.

The interview will take approximately an hour.

With your consent, the interview will be audio-recorded.

You can skip any question or stop the interview at any time.

Your identity will be kept confidential unless you request otherwise. All names and identifying details will be anonymised.

Recordings will be stored securely and used only for academic purposes.

Participation is voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time without penalty.

Okay noted

.....

Consent Declaration

Please tick to confirm *

I have read and understood the information above. 1

I voluntarily agree to take part in this interview.

I understand that my participation in this research is voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time without any negative consequences.

Participant details

Name of the Participant(optional)

.....

Date

.....

19 June 2025

Signature(Type your full name as consent)

.....

Tupochele Milanzi

Researcher Details

Researcher: Samuel Malasa Banda
MA Public Affairs and Political Communication
School of Media
Technological University Dublin
East Quad
Grangegorman
Dublin 7
Ireland.

Yes

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Appendix 3: Full Interview Transcript (sample)

Participant Profile

Participant ID: P01

Gender: Male

Age (in 2019): 22

Location (Urban Area): Zomba

Occupation/Education Status (in 2019): 4th Year University Student – Chancellor College

Type of Institution Attended: Public University

Social Media Usage in 2019: Active daily on Facebook and WhatsApp

Access Method in 2019: Own smartphone

Language Preference on Facebook: Chichewa and English

Voting Status in 2019: Voted in the May 2019 Presidential Election

Date of Interview: 13 June 2025, 05:06pm

- **Interviewer (Samuel)** started transcription

Interviewer (Samuel) 0:13

Welcome to this conversation. In this research basically we are talking about the use and meaning of social media usage among young people in Malawi. Please feel free to answer the questions that you feel very comfortable with, and if there are some questions which you are not comfortable to answer feel free to skip them. And if it happens that you feel like the conversation should end at some point also feel free to inform me that you would like the interview to end. So first I would like to thank you for agreeing to take part in this interview, which will take approximately an hour. As I said I am conducting this research as part of my master's in public affairs in political communication studies at TU Dublin, and I'm mostly interested in understanding how young people in Malawi used social media around the 2019 presidential election. What kind of content they engaged with and how it made them feel and what it meant to them. So I would just like to let you know that there's no pressure to give perfect answers because this is about your story and your experience. And everything that you will share with me will be treated confidentially and it will only be used for academic purposes.

Participant 1 2:04

Thank you so much. I'm okay having a conversation with you. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 2:12

Alright so as a starter, can you just tell me a bit about yourself?

Participant 1 2:20

Alright maybe to understand your question. I should tell you about myself as in what I do and all that?

Interviewer (Samuel) 2:33

Yes, you can tell me in anything about yourself or everything that you can comfortably share about you as a person.

Participant 1 2:47

Alright thank you so much. I am a development practitioner, mainly in education projects. I'm interested in seeing the change which I would want to see in people. Especially helping the most vulnerable children in the communities to stay in school, especially at an age appropriate. I am a teacher by profession and I am interested in seeing that children are able to read and write. And by the way, my name is Participant number 1. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 3:32

Alright. Would you be comfortable to share with me maybe your actual age or your age range, where you live and your qualifications anything like that?

Participant 1 3:42

Alright thank you so much. I am 29 years old. I hold a bachelors in education science. I majored in chemistry and minored in mathematics. I am currently working with World Vision Malawi in Mchinji district. So that's basically who I am and my qualifications. I'm also currently studying for my Master's degree in project management at the University of Malawi. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 4:21

Alright thank you very much for that. So as I had alluded that our conversation this evening has to do with social media. So basically, I would like to know, how did you get started using social media?

Participant 1 4:43

After completing my secondary education in 2013 I attended a youth retreat that was organized by Students Christian Organization of Malawi, SCOM. In 2013 it was called the school leavers retreat and there were a number of lessons and topic which were tackled. And one of the topics which was provided by that time was that as youths, we have to follow and understand the current affairs and one of the ways of capturing or understanding the

current affairs is in the use of social media and I got introduced into a number of social media platforms including Facebook, Twitter. Yeah, basically I joined Facebook in 2013. By now I think it's over a lot of years, I don't know the number of years, but I've been using it since 2013. So that's how I was introduced to social media. I created an account and I started using Facebook and twitter and I interacted with my friends and also it was as a means of getting what is out there in the world, what are the current affairs of that time and also the fact that I was a school leaver I was looking for opportunities which would arise and one of the ways of getting the opportunities was through social media. So that's how I joined the social media. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 6:40

That's interesting. So you have shared about how you started using social media. Now I'm interested that in the modern day, can you tell me, how do you use social media?

Participant 1 6:55

In the modern day, basically, social media is the one sources of information, where we get to know, as I said, one of the reasons why I joined social media hasn't changed. It is about getting the updates, getting the current affairs. But social media is somehow different with the mainstream media. For example, the issue of newspapers or the printing media, when they hear a story that has come up, they will have to first write this story and then they will have to go to the editors and the story which took place today you might see in the newspapers tomorrow. Whilst the social media, the trending stories are there. It has happened now you go on social media; you'll find it there. So, one of the reasons why, or rather one of the uses of social media personally is the current affairs and sources of some vital information which I might need and as well as connecting with my friends. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 8:21

Alright great. You mentioned that when you were introduced to social media, there were a couple of platforms or applications that you were introduced to. So, do you think that since then has your social media usage changed over time? Or maybe, let's say, do you prefer one platform over the other? Or maybe do you spend more time on one platform over the other? Or maybe if you can know what has caused that change, if you've experienced any change on that?

Participant 1 8:56

Alright as I said, I was first introduced to Facebook and Twitter by then. However, I should admit that I'm not very active on Twitter. Maybe one of the reasons is that Twitter for me is very complicated as compared to Facebook. So, I prefer using Facebook than Twitter and I

spend so much of my time on Facebook than Twitter. I use Twitter maybe once in a week but I am always available on Facebook. So, one of the reasons is that to me Facebook is user friendly. It's easy to get information and also, some of the tabs on Facebook are in the easy to navigate than those on the Twitter application. And also, personally I have observed that, a lot of people use Facebook here in Malawi more than they do with Twitter and a lot of trending stories and a lot of information is posted on Facebook rather than Twitter. So that's why I use Facebook more as compared to twitter.

Interviewer (Samuel) 10:32

So it would be right to say one of the reasons why you are inclined towards Facebook as compared to Twitter and other social media platforms is because you feel there are a lot of people on Facebook that you can connect with as compared to other platforms right?

Participant 1 10:51

Yes, that is right.

Interviewer (Samuel) 10:55

So you've shared that there are a lot of things, maybe there's a lot of content generated via Facebook or on social media in general. I'm interested to know what kind of stuff do you usually look at on social media or for you to be precise, on Facebook, what kind of stuff, what kind of content do you usually like to interact with or to look at?

Participant 1 11:23

Well, I mostly interact with Politics. Understanding how Politics is going, how things are being shaped in the political world and how that is affecting our day-to-day life, and also how politics is playing a role in the economy of Malawi. So if I would be asked if I interact with the politics content more than the other content I'd say yes. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 12:04

How do you interact with this political content? I'm interested to know, because let's say there are videos, there are just text news, there are photos, there are live streams, there are debates. If we can go towards that, to say, I would like to understand that in these different streams of content that is shared, that might be political, there are pages, there are groups, there are communities, so how do you interact with this political content?

Participant 1 12:38

Alright. So we have social media influences. Where a lot of, for example, pages that might be managed by some of the well-known people in Malawi and those people here in Malawi, we refer them as social media influencers. So mostly I interact with their pages and maybe they are putting in the texts and also the videos I would say I interact more with the texts and the

videos as compared to maybe live streams and the other types of content.

Interviewer (Samuel) 13:31

Okay so using the word interacting at times it's a bit vague. It might carry a meaning that is not intended, so I would like to know that by saying that you interact does this mean you like, you comment, you share, like what kind of interaction do you do? Or if someone say something that you agree with, do you go to comment on that? If someone says something that you think is not, right? Do you go and argue? Maybe just try to give me a picture narrative of how you interact with such kind of content on social media?

Participant 1 14:10

Alright. So basically, my interaction on social media is not about commenting or writing or sharing, but rather just reading, going through the content that is being shared. But in the background, I might have a conversation with some of my friends to say, Okay. Or maybe I will take a screenshot of what has been posted on social media or maybe I will get a link to that post and send it to them and then we can be discussing those things privately, maybe on a call or maybe on WhatsApp. And we'll just be discussing with friends, but not necessarily liking, sharing or even commenting. I am not very good at commenting or liking or sharing because I do not want to be seen as someone who is inclined to a political party. So that's why I just leave it as it is. I just go through the shared news and then If I have some things to share or maybe some insights that I want to discuss about, I discuss that with my close friends whom we share a lot of things in common. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 15:33

So in other words, you are saying you avoid making public comments on social media because you don't want to be labelled to belong to some area or political party or something like that.

Participant 1 15:45

Exactly.

Interviewer (Samuel) 15:49

Alright, so I'm interested to know, can you tell me about a powerful or memorable experience that you have had through social media. Like one memorable powerful experience that whenever you remember, you know that this was the most powerful memory I have ever experienced and that it all happened through social media or when I was using social media.

Participant 1 16:19

Alright yes, I will get back to 2019 during the campaign period when Malawi had the

elections. We had a President by then and a certain population of the nation was not in agreement and shared that we needed change. So that had a lot of impact on social media because a lot of people who were pushing for change were the youth and I think a lot of people took it to social media where they were pushing for some of the things including the widespread demonstrations which were there, that was soon after 2019 presidential election, which a lot of people thought that It had a lot of illegalities and they wanted a change, and when the case was in court a lot of people were getting a lot of updates from social media. For me it was on Facebook and WhatsApp where we were getting some of the updates about what is happening in the world especially Malawi. Nowadays I'm not a very good fan of the radio, where a lot of information is shared, so I get up to date information using social media. So that experience the 2019 presidential election campaign, post 2019 election results and also the fresh presidential election, which occurred in 2020 was a very interesting period because it got us all thinking and it gave us curiosity to still go on social media and check what is happening on Facebook. What is it that is happening elsewhere? How the demonstrations which are happening in Mzuzu and what is happening at the court? Some people were even interpreting some of the issues happening in court, maybe the witnesses. When they were giving their testimony in court, some people would even start analyzing what was happening in court. So, it gives me curiosity to continue being on social media and seeing and talking about what is happening and also understanding what is happening and how it will shape our future. So, that was one of the most interesting periods that I've ever had using social media. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 19:39

Alright. So, for you your opinion is that social media had a huge influence in how people followed the 2019 elections case is that what you're trying to say? That's what I would like to understand.

Participant 1 19:59

For my perspective social media indeed had a very profound influence on people during that period.

Interviewer (Samuel) 20:11

Alright. So, the next thing that I would like to know, as a person, do you think your social media reflects who you are offline. Or like whatever you do on social media, is it a reflection of who you are as a person or how do the two interplays? Your social media personality and your offline personality, how do the two relate?

Participant 1 20:37

Alright as for me, the person that I am offline is the same person I am on social media. My personality on social media doesn't change who I am. I have my beliefs and I have my values which I take to heart and I do not compromise just because I'm on social media. I'm still the same person.

Interviewer (Samuel) 21:04

Alright. I'm asking because you had earlier explained to say, you can just follow things on social media. I'm just using this as an example. You follow things on social media and then you discuss it with other people, those you can trust. So, if its political content offline, is it the same that you also just listen and discuss with the people you know? I hope you get what I'm trying to say.

Participant 1 21:34

Yes yes I get it. If that would be used as an example then I would say, I'm a political person that's why most of the times I go on social media and I interact mostly with the political content but then I do not want to be labelled that I belong to a certain party, basically because I do not have a political party which I support. And when we are discussing the information offline, we discuss it on a neutral ground, and we just discuss what are the pros and cons of what is happening, maybe for a certain political party but not necessarily that I belong to a certain political party. So, because I would want to be maintained as someone who does not belong or support a certain political party, that's why I avoid interacting, liking or sharing some of the content on social media. So, if you would understand that in that way, then I will say that I'm still the same person.

Interviewer (Samuel) 22:51

Alright. So, moving on, how do people around you, for instance, your friends, family, classmates, workmates, what influence or do they have any influence on how you use social media?

Participant 1 23:11

Yes, I would say so. Because I will explain that by using an example. So initially I am agreeing that people around me influence how I use my social media because if someone shares me content, If a friend shares a certain content to me, maybe using a link or using maybe a screen shot, I first of all have to understand the person. Who is this person? and why is he sharing what he's shared and what he shared also helps me to think okay, what is the other content rather that I can be interacting with on social media. For example, if someone shares a certain story or a certain post from someone maybe talking about marriage and then I would basically if I was not following the person, but interacting with the post and also

looking at the other post which they share, I would follow the person just to continue engaging with the content that they share. So, if we understand it from that angle, then I would say that I am influenced by the other people on the use of my social media. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 24:43

Alright thank you. So, I would like to know that, what accounts, pages or individuals do you find most important or influential on social media and why?

Participant 1 24:59

I want to understand that question properly, do you want me to mention the pages or the types of the pages which I follow.

Interviewer (Samuel) 25:11

Alright. You can mention the people, whether the accounts, you can do a mix of both that you think okay, I follow this page because I find it influential or because of ABCD or whatever way that you might choose to approach it. I'm open to that.

Participant 1 25:34

Okay thank you so much. One of the pages that I follow are the pages for the radio stations which are in mainstream media. For example, we have Zodiac, we have Times 360 then we have Mibawa and all other pages for the radio stations which are here in Malawi. I follow those because, I find their content authentic. So, I'm looking at the authenticity of the content that they share, If they are sharing something, it means that it is verified and it is authentic, something which we can trust. And also, the other influential pages which I follow or for the social media influencers or for example, one of the pages that I follow is the page for Onjezani Kenani. He shares vital information which also sometimes shape the direction of some of the issues which are happening in Malawi. So some of the influential pages which I follow, I follow them just because I find them authentic. Whilst some other pages I follow them because I just find them fun and I go there to relax maybe for example actors here in Malawi and what they are sharing, that's basically some of the pages which I follow and why I follow them. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 27:33

Alright so I think the next question was supposed to look at if you have ever held back from commenting or sharing something online because of how others might respond. But I think in our introductory part, you already alluded to why or why you do not share and why you do not engage with certain content. So going to the next question, I would like to know that, have you ever come across posts or social media content that turned out to be false or misleading.

Participant 1 28:03

Yes. I have come across such information that was posted and it was misleading and some authentic pages they retracted and ended up giving a public apology and some other pages which are not that authentic, maybe just pages of individuals they may either retract, or they may just joke around it so that it should be seen as if they did not commit an error. But I've ever come across such information, such posts which was misleading and false on social media.

Interviewer (Samuel) 28:49

Alright. I know it might be asking too much of you, but would you have at least one that you can easily recall? If you don't, its fine, but if you do have maybe one scenario that you recall that you came across something that was posted and then it later turned out to be false or misleading. Do you have such example in mind?

Participant 1 29:11

Currently I don't remember any. But if I can be given a bit of time, I'll recall because my mind somehow is locked. Yeah, but in some cases, we've ever had that.

Interviewer (Samuel) 29:27

Alright that's fine. So now my interest is after you saw this information that turned out to be false or misleading. How did that affect your trust or your use of social media platforms?

Participant 1 29:49

Alright. It changed my perspective because sometimes, especially when people are putting out posts for breaking news or if they would want to break the news most of the times some information that is misleading it's because some people want to be the first ones to break the news that has happened. So that had to give me a bit of time first of all not to trust every information that is posted. And if that has been posted by a certain page, I would have go to another page just to verify if this information is true? If it is not true, what is the truth behind this information? So, I have to gather the information from different sources so that I should find the right information that I'm seeking. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 30:58

Alright. So, thinking back to the 2019 elections, like you said, that you spent most time following news on social media. What do you remember about how people maybe including yourself were using social media during the 2019 elections?

Participant 1 31:19

It had different aspects depending on who is posting and also who are the outlets, the social media outlets and what is the purpose behind what they are sharing? So, for some of us, and

for some people, it was just to go there and get the current affairs just to get the update of what is happening in the world. Whilst for some people they used the social media as the campaign tool to campaign for their favorite political leaders. We had different individuals by then, the current President, Dr Lazarus Chakwera, we had the late Vice President Dr. Saulos Chilima and then we also had the former Professor Peter Mutharika. So, some people were using social media as a campaign tool to campaign for their candidates. So, they were mostly posting information which was either to favor their candidate or maybe just to tarnish the image of the opponents. So, whilst for some of us, it was just to interact with people, while for some individuals it was to have debates on who is to win and who is not going to win and what the reasons are, and just to provide some of those aspects on the platform. So that's how it got used.

Interviewer (Samuel) 33:16

Okay so for you during that time you said people were campaigning, others were doing all that, like what kind of political or election related content stood out to you during that time like what you think this would always come to your feed or you would always go searching for it? What kind of political election related content stood out to you on social media during the 2019 elections?

Participant 1 33:43

For me it was how one presidential candidate by then shaped the campaign in 2019 and also 2020 that is the late Dr. Saulos Klaus Chilima and how he moved around the nation campaigning to be elected as a president and also how he changed the narratives of how people should campaign. As a youthful leader he related much to us the youth, for example, doing pushups on the podium or using words which are relatable to the youth, for example “musamangoshala anyamata”. So that is a chichewa word which means, don't just be idle young people but let's keep on pushing. So, I'd go back to his campaign trail time and again, just seeing how he was campaigning for the chair during the campaign period and also the powerful speeches that he was delivering and also how he promised people that Malawi is going to change if he is to be elected as the president. So that was what stood out for me and the I will always refer to the campaigns that have been happening since the I have been alive but this stood out for me to be one of the best campaign times that we've ever had. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 35:42

Alright so in your opinion, do you think social media has changed how people think about politics, or how involved or informed they felt during that specific elections? What's your

take on that?

Participant 1 35:58

I would say social media played a role because for people to get to know how, I would give an example of how Saulos Klaus Chilima was campaigning, mostly it was through the use of social media. You know, a lot of people, the youthful people which this was being targeted, most of them are employed and maybe they wouldn't have a lot of time to watch the television in their homes. But using Facebook, live streaming, using Twitter and also the other platforms or even sharing on WhatsApp on what is happening, some of the audios, people got to know how presidential candidates who were campaigning for themselves and what was happening where, and that also shaped the how people perceive politics in Malawi. So, I would say it had played a role in how people perceive politics in Malawi, not only for that campaign, but even for this campaign, in this time around where people are doing the campaigns for 2025 presidential election. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) 37:27

Alright. You have spoken more on a general level, but if I were to zoom in and be a bit specific like how were people your age engaging with politics online during that time? Like people in your age range, like young people in Malawi, how were they engaging with politics online during the 2019 elections?

Participant 1 37:50

Okay so people of my age during 2019 election, they were engaging more on politics from my perspective, number one, with the use of social media and also the fact that we had a youthful leader who was almost everyone's favorite and how they were campaigning, so I would say most of the times in the groups, for example in the WhatsApp groups which I was in and also the pages which I was following like on Facebook, most of the youth of my age were discussing politics as compared to any other content that was being done by then or being shared by then.

Interviewer (Samuel) 38:38

Alright. So, as we are coming towards the end, I would like to know that do you feel that being online as compared to those maybe who were offline. As in being online during the 2019 elections had any impact on how people in Malawi think about politics or how they think about their role as a citizen? Do you feel that being online during 2019 has shaped or has had an impact on how people think about politics and their role in a democratic Malawi?

Participant 1 39:11

Yes to be specific for 2019, I'd say social media had an impact on the role of citizens in

Malawi. Basically, because a lot of people we are discussing politics as I said and also, they were encouraging each other to go and vote because a lot of people believed that we needed a change and they said change wouldn't come if we just remain quiet and the a lot of people were discussing, they were sharing and they were encouraging one another to go and vote. There were also even some groups which were being formed just to discuss how they would guard the votes. To be monitors for some political parties and also to be involved in some of the strategies that were being made to control the rigging of the votes by then, because a lot of people had believed that the votes are being left unprotected for some candidates and they said, let us control the votes, let us control the rigging of the votes. So it came from people interacting on pages on social media and some other groups were being formed just to make sure they were discussing how they would guard the votes, so I would say social media played a crucial role on the citizens during the 2019 elections.

Interviewer (Samuel) 41:04

Alright thank you very much. In my last question, I would just like to know, is there anything else that you would like to share or is there anything that we haven't talked about but you had it in mind to share?

Participant 1 41:19

Yes, I would like to say as we've had this discussion, we've seen how social media has impacted citizens, but yes it has been both positive and negative. In some cases, for example, nowadays some people are discouraged from going to vote. I wouldn't give an example in 2019 because, as I said in 2019, it was social media which was influencing people to vote whilst as of now, people are saying there's no reason for us to go and vote because some I would say they have been demotivated and discouraged with how the political leaders they trusted have been performing. So, social media has both positive and negative, and it is the role of the one who is using it to sieve what is important and what is not important and how they can use the information that they are getting from social media. And as I said, there is no control with the use of social media despite some of the roles which are there to monitor the use. But in most of the cases there's no control. Everyone can just post what they are thinking and that sometimes might be misleading, or maybe it may also have a certain impact on other people's reputation. So, there's a need for people to be responsible when they're using social media. Thank you so much.

Interviewer (Samuel) 43:13

Alright. So, I would like to thank you for giving me at least 53 minutes of your time that we could have this conversation. As I said at the beginning, that everything that has been said

here is confidential and will be used strictly for academic purposes.

● **Participant 1** 43:37

Alright thank you so much for having me to contribute towards your research and I'm looking forward to your success. Thank you.

Interviewer (Samuel) stopped transcription

Appendix 4: Thematic Coding Color Key

Platform Use and Affordances

Uses and Gratifications – Information, Expressive, Social

Identity and Symbolic Meaning

Misinformation and Trust

Peer and Community Dynamics

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 1:23

Sure. So, to start, can you tell me about yourself?

Participant 13 1:31

I'm Participant 13.

I'm currently working as an Enacting Call Centre team leader for First Capital Bank.

I hold a bachelor's degree in communications and cultural studies.

In my spare time, I like to watch news, movies and I had an interest in politics, but recently I think my focus has shifted. I focus more on work than the other stuff.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 2:12

OK, thank you. If you can just share with me, there are two options. People are comfortable. They're either telling me their actual age or they give me an age range. I think that's it.

Participant 13 2:12

OK so my age range is between 35 and 40.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 2:39

Right, good. Alright. So thank you very much.

Now, I would like to know that how did you get started using social media?

Participant 13 2:53

I think I was first introduced to social media, especially Facebook.

I think that should be 2003.

Yes, 2003 and I was there maybe for four or five years. Then I deleted my account. I stayed maybe for two or three years without it. Then I was back on Facebook in 2006. Since then I have had the current profile that I have.

Yeah, I was introduced by my sister.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 3:49

Ok, so that was back then 2005, 2006.

I would like to know that.

How do you use social media like in your life like right now?

Participant 13 4:07

Now because I don't post anything

I just use it to check out the news

So when I wake up in the morning, I always go to Facebook to check the news. Like what's happening today, or what happened yesterday. Let's say, like today during the weekends, I don't usually use Facebook. So Mondays when I wake up in the morning, I usually go to Facebook. I check Zodiak and Times

And then I also go to BBC, and the rest if I have time. Then I proceed with my day. Around maybe lunch hour, I also have time to check what's happening or what's going on. I don't usually use it to connect with people, especially Facebook. I only use it to check what's happening. The entertainment side and also the news.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 5:16

You came to know about social media and so on in 2003, and then you joined Facebook in 2006, I would like to know from then to today, has your social media usage changed over time, if it has changed, what might have caused those changes?

Participant 13 5:33

Yes, it has changed because I think the past years I was usually posting pictures, changing my profile, maybe liking posts and commenting, but I think for the past 2-3 or four years I haven't done so much.

Because I think I'm leaving a more private life now. I don't know why, but maybe because I'm getting older. So I don't like those things anymore. I have shifted my use of Facebook to just checking out the news and everything that is just happening.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 6:25

There are so many social media channels you've mentioned Facebook, but there are others and there's radio and there's newspapers. I would like to know when it comes to getting news or political content, which platform do you prefer, and if you prefer one platform over the other, what could be the reasons why you prefer that platform?

Participant 13 6:50

I think I don't listen to the radio.

I don't remember the last time I listened to the radio.

I watch TV now and then, but not so much. But because social media, especially Facebook, has an easy reach, you just take your phone and you log in and you have the access. There's no need for you to sit down and listen to the radio, you can move about with your phone you can read anywhere, so it's easier. So that's why I think I tend to use Facebook for news than watching the TV where I need to be stationed in one place and watch instead of maybe using the phone, I can be in a minibus or even cooking. You can be reading on your phone, put it down then continue cooking. Yeah, so I think Facebook has an easy access to the news. That's why I think I'm using it more than the other channels.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 8:04

Ok. I know you said this, but on a typical day when you get on Facebook or on social media, what are the things that you look at? Again, I think you mentioned one or two things that you like. What are those things? What kind of content do you usually look at?

Participant 13 8:21

OK. First, it's the news. Then I go to the entertainment section, especially from Mikozi. I read, I check their page, and I think maybe I also check pages of a few people that I follow on Facebook just to see what they have posted.

Yeah, I think that's what I do.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 9:23

Thank you. So can you tell me about a powerful, memorable experience that you have had through social media? You know, there are some things that when we remember them, we remember them through the lens of social media or, you know, that when this happened, it happened because of social media.

Participant 13 9:48

There are so many.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 9:50

OK.

Participant 13 9:51

Let me remember the recent one.

I think learning that the aeroplane carrying the Vice president had vanished from the radar. I think that's that was a memorable experience that I got through Facebook.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 10:26

It was about a year ago, right?

Tupochele Milazi

Yes.

I'm trying to think of a more recent event.

But it's not coming.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 10:50

OK, let's stick with that. That's fine.

So I would like to know do you think your social media presence reflects who you are as a person.

Participant 13 11:04

Yes it does.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 11:07

Ok.

Participant 13 11:07

Because, I think some of the pages that I follow can define who I am.

If I follow more entertainment pages, that means my focus and my character, anything else is defined by that, but if maybe, I read more of the news, that's also a definition of my character that I'm more focused on learning what's happening out there.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 11:53

Alright. What about the content that you post or where you comment? Do you think those things reflect who you are as a person?

Participant 13 12:04

Yes it does. Let's say for me, I'm more focused on the political news.

And I think in the past week I've been more focused on the war that is going on between Israel and Iran. So before I go to sleep, I have to check what's happening and when I wake up, I also have to check.

Have they dropped bombs on Iran or Israel today?

Yeah.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 12:44

Right. So now I'd like to know, you are someone who said you work at the bank or in the banking sector, you have gone to school and you have friends, you have people around you. I would like to know, how do these people around you influence how you use your social media?

Participant 13 13:03

Like my family, they are into the entertainment side or just the stories that are happening in life. So every time that they see something interesting, let's say Mikozi has posted that something has happened in maybe Mulanje, they will text you and ask that have you checked Mikozi, they have posted this story.

So when we come together, we'll talk about the story. So I think I'm influenced by my family or my friends on the stories that I read.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 13:48

Alright, so you did mention this at the beginning and you've already referenced to Mikozi, but I just want to still check what pages or individuals do you find most important or influential in your social media usage.

Participant 13 14:04

I'll say my sister Tina.

And I think she's the closest person to me, I'll say she's the one that influences me to be checking out these stories. And there's my mom. She also likes the news. So every time I get home, she's like, have you seen the news today? Israel has done this and that, Yeah. So I think these two people.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 14:35

OK. What about, like maybe let's say, social media pages that you always follow that you get your news or you check often? what are these pages or accounts or individuals on Facebook or on social media generally that you follow?

Participant 13 14:55

OK. So within Malawi, yes.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 14:59

Yeah, you can be within or even out outside. I'm OK.

Participant 13 15:01

OK, so I'll say I follow Jared Kampanikiza and Julius Ziwanda Mithi, when I want to check

the local news or what's happening within, so I go to these guys' pages.

I don't usually use Nation newspaper but I check Zodiak, Times.

And for international stories, I think recently I'm liking Sky News.

I think these are the pages that I like.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 15:53

OK, so I would like to know in your using of social media, have you ever come across a post that turned out to be false or misleading?

Participant 13 16:08

Yes.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 16:13

Can you remember anything that you can recall?

Participant 13 16:20

So, I think the past week or the past two weeks, there was a story on MBC news page.

I think it was shared by MCP guys that Peter Mutharika is in South Africa, and he's Sick.

And from what I've seen when he was coming back, I don't think he was sick. No one can verify that he was sick, but the story was there.

There's so many stories, especially from the guys that have mentioned. They usually post fake stories and I think I've seen one today. They're saying Peter Mutharika has withdrawn from the presidential contest.

And later on he posted that it was fake, so yes.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 17:20

OK.

So when you come across this posts that are fake and maybe later on you come to know that they are fake, how does this or how did that affect your trust or your use of social media?

Participant 13 17:39

OK, so I think using social media over the years, I think I've learned not to trust the post that I see before verifying the information, of course, sometimes it's not easy to verify information, but we just wait that maybe someone or something will come up that will verify the information.

So maybe for the first 3-4 hours you just say I've seen something, but I'm not sure if it's true.

So maybe sometimes it ends up to be the truth. Sometimes it ends up to be false, but I think

for me, my trust on these pages is I think 70% because most of the times the stories that they write turn out to be true.

A larger percentage of the stories are true and the other percentage is just an exaggeration of the truth.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 19:04

All right, so now, we are moving to the 2019 elections. I tend to give a warning about two things, firstly, this is about six years ago, so it's easy to forget some things and that's okay. Secondly, people tend to talk about the 2020 elections. They tend to mix up 2019 and 2020 elections or people are often tempted to talk about the upcoming 2025 elections, which I

really understand, but my focus is on the 2019 election.

So, thinking back to the 2019 elections, what do you remember about how people maybe even including yourself were using social media in 2019?

Participant 13 19:55

OK, I think in 2019 there were a lot of posts about the election, so you could comment, read and get the information that was being shared mostly by the parties, followers and supporters. I think we were getting most of our news, the promises that the presidential candidates were making, we would get them through Facebook posts.

Yeah, just the information about the elections was shared through the posts.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 20:50

Right. So for you as a user, when you look back or try to retrace in your memory what kind of elections or political content stood out to you during that time? By this I mean something that you know that there was so much content flooding social media, but there was a particular kind of content maybe from a particular political that you know this was good content because of this and that. What kind of content like that stood out to you during the 2019 election?

Participant 13 21:46

Yeah.

OK, so I think for 2019 the campaign for Chakwera maybe stood out for me because he was kind of new.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 22:32

Was Chakwera's campaign in 2019 or 2014?

Participant 13 22:36

2014 he was a student, 2014.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 22:38

Chakwera first stood in 2014.

Yes, I'm remembering because Chakwera's first presidential race was when I was at Polytechnic in 2013, so he first stood as an MCP presidential candidate in 2014, the first one to stand in 2019 was Chilima.

Participant 13 22:47

Can we talk about Chilima?

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 23:10

No. You can talk about anything. I was just trying to give you context. I just wanted to say that the 2019 election wasn't Chakwera's first standing as an MCP candidate.

Participant 13 23:16

So, I'm even surprised that I don't remember much.

I think Chilima was the one people's we're talking about, a youthful president Yeah. So it was all about let's vote for Chilima.

He's young, he has fresh ideas and he's going to change the country.

I think most of the content was about that, a youthful president, yes.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 24:01

So now I would like to know do you think social media in 2019 changed how people were involved in that election or how people were informed during the election?

Participant 13 24:15

Yes, because I think 2019 also changed how people used social media during elections, there was a lot of access to information through Facebook.

Because I think by then a lot of people had gotten access to social media through phones, computers compared to the last election.

It was easier to communicate to people. It was easier to send information to people because a lot of people had access.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 25:06

OK. So let's try to zero into a certain population that is young people.

How were young people engaging with politics online, on social media during the 2019 elections?

Participant 13 25:25

OK, so let's say there was a post that was made by maybe follower of Chilima and they will write down the things that Chilima would do if he got elected, and so that post would be shared among the youth and they will comment. In the comment they'll be saying chilima is young compared to Peter Mutharika, who is old. Let's vote for him. So I think that also ignited another conversation that this is the president that we're supposed to vote for, compared to this President, because of the age gap and because of the ideas that he had. He had worked with Airtel it was doing good under his leadership. So if we vote for him, Malawi is going to change. I think most of the things were like that.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 26:34

OK. And finally, as we come to the end, do you feel that being online during the 2019 elections had any impact on how people think about politics in Malawi or how they view their role as citizens in a democratic country?

Participant 13 26:53

Yes. So let's say I have not gotten on Facebook and I had no access to Facebook.

There's some information that I will miss out on.

But if I have access to Facebook and maybe I have seen a post, it might not be true. But the fact that I've read something, it will make me decide if I have to vote for this person because of this. So I think over time when you see a lot of posts on some things they can influence your decision that I think this is the right person that I need to vote for. So yes, Facebook or social media, indeed influenced people during the election time.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 27:46

And finally, is there anything else you would like to share or is there anything we haven't talked about that you think is relevant to this research and maybe I didn't ask about it?

Participant 13 28:09

No.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda 28:12

- Alright. With that, I would like to thank you for making time for this conversation. Again, I would like to assure you that everything that has been said here will be used confidentially for academic purposes only and if, however, I use a quote from everything that we've said, it will be anonymised so it cannot be traced back to you. But overall, thank you that you could make time that we have this conversation.

Participant 13 28:38

Welcome.

D24127399 Samuel Malasa Banda stopped transcription

Appendix 5: Establishing categories and themes

After generating the initial descriptive codes from the interview transcripts, the next step in my analysis was to regroup these codes into preliminary categories and, ultimately, overarching themes (Seale, 2018). To do this, I reviewed all codes and clustered similar ones together to form sub-categories and broader categories. This process allowed me to move beyond individual codes to identify recurring patterns across participants' accounts. The final stage involved refining these categories into key themes that captured the central meanings in the data. A simplified example of this process is provided below for the theme of *Platform Use and Affordances*.

Themes	Categories	Sub-categories	Example from interview
Platform Use & Affordances	Facebook as central arena	Election news / Real-time updates	“Facebook during that time? It was everything... That’s where we got results, where MEC would post things...” (P08)
	WhatsApp as private space	Trusted conversations / Mobilisation	“Facebook is like a big public square... But WhatsApp is where I have more meaningful conversations with people I trust.” (P16)
	Strategic Platform avoidance	Avoiding Twitter, Instagram, TikTok	“I had Twitter, but I did not use it much during the elections... Facebook felt closer to home.” (P06)
	Varied modes of interactions	Silent engagement / Liking / Sharing / Debating	“I followed the elections so closely, but I never commented... I would just scroll, read, click links, and sometimes screenshot.” (P15)